

22DIT01 – ViDiT

D4: User's guide for the software repository including well-documented examples and templates (e.g. Python notebooks) for the users to use and adapt

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable:

VTT

Due date of the deliverable:

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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Table of Contents

1	How to get started.....	4
1.1	Availability and access.....	4
1.2	Directory structure.....	4
1.3	Licence4	
1.4	Disclaimer	5
2	Software for uncertainty evaluation using virtual experiments.....	6
2.1	Uncertainty evaluation for the tilted-wave interferometer	6
2.1.1	Where can I find the implementation?.....	6
2.1.2	What are the requirements?	6
2.1.3	Do I need additional data to run the implementation?	6
2.1.4	Where do I start?.....	7
2.2	Uncertainty evaluation for the coordinate measuring machine	8
2.2.1	Location and access	8
2.2.2	Programming language and requirements	8
2.2.3	FAIR dataset.....	8
2.2.4	Content and short description	8
2.2.5	Examples	9
2.3	Uncertainty evaluation for the flow-meter measurements	10
2.3.1	Programming Language and Requirements.....	11
2.3.2	Content and Usage.....	11
2.3.3	Documentation and configuration	12
2.3.4	FAIR Dataset.....	12
3	Software for uncertainty evaluation using digital twins	13
3.1	Uncertainty evaluation for nanoindentation	13
3.1.1	Location and Access.....	13
3.1.2	Programming language and requirements	13
3.1.3	FAIR dataset.....	13
3.1.4	Where do I start?.....	14
3.2	Uncertainty evaluation for reference rotary table measurements.....	16
3.3	Uncertainty evaluation for optical machine-vision measurement	18
3.4	Uncertainty evaluation for electrical measurements	20
3.4.1	High voltage measurement	20
3.4.2	Internal arc test.....	24
3.4.3	Quantum voltage standard.....	33
4	References	40
1	ANNEX – SPACS – SOFTWARE FOR HIGH VOLTAGE APPLICATION1	
1.1	Introduction	1
1.2	Interface.....	1
1.3	Main toolbar	1
1.4	Creating a new circuit	3
1.4.1	Inserting and configuring underground cables and overhead line sections	3
1.4.2	Types of section.....	4
1.4.3	Voltage sources.....	8
1.5	Configure sections.....	9

1.5.1	Modification of underground section data.....	10
1.6	Steady state study. Study of loaded power lines.	12
1.7	Study in time-domain analysis. Short-circuits in power lines.	13
1.8	Results of the study	14
1.8.1	Use case	17
1.8.2	Introduction to the uncertainty evaluation	19
1.8.3	Interface for the uncertainty evaluation in static mode.....	20
1.8.4	Results of the uncertainty evaluation in static mode	21
1.8.5	Use case	21
1.8.6	Uncertainty evaluation in dynamic analysis	25
2	Annex – Documentation for TWI benchmarking scenario and uncertainty evaluation methods.....	30

1 How to get started

This report contains a detailed description of the software developed and the data provided in the 22DIT01 project ViDiT “Trustworthy virtual experiments and digital twins”. The actual software is available open source at <https://gitlab1.ptb.de/vidit-group/ViDiT Software> and can be downloaded as a whole, including all required datasets.

1.1 Availability and access

The actual open source software repository is available at PTB’s Gitlab server <https://gitlab1.ptb.de/vidit-group/ViDiT Software> and can be downloaded as a whole, including all required datasets, from the following Zenodo community <https://zenodo.org/communities/vidit/>

In the following sections, it is assumed that the whole repository has been downloaded, including all datasets.

1.2 Directory structure

The software is structured according to their interpretation as a virtual experiment (VE), which were treated in Work package (WP) one, or as a digital twin (DT), discussed in WP2, respectively. Subsequently, each application and use-case is represented by its own directory.

Figure 1. Overview of directory structure of ViDiT Software repository available at (ViDiT - 22DIT01, 2026).

1.3 Licence

Copyright ViDiT – 22DIT01 2024-2026

This software is licensed under the BSD-like license:

Redistribution and use in source and binary forms, with or without modification, are permitted provided that the following conditions are met:

1. Redistributions of source code must retain the above copyright notice, this list of conditions and the following disclaimer.
2. Redistributions in binary form must reproduce the above copyright notice, this list of conditions and the following disclaimer in the documentation and/or other materials provided with the distribution.

1.4 Disclaimer

This software was developed in the European Partnership project ViDiT. The software is provided “as is”, without warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the warranties of merchantability, fitness for a particular purpose and noninfringement. In no event shall the authors, the consortium or partners of ViDiT, EURAMET, or the copyright holders be liable for any claim, damages or other liability, whether in an action of contract, tort or otherwise, arising from, out of or in connection with the software or the use or other dealings in the software.

2 Software for uncertainty evaluation using virtual experiments

The software repository and this section of the report is aligned with the applications considered in the project that involve virtual experiments, which were discussed in WP1: The tilted-wave interferometer (TWI), the coordinate measuring machine (CMM) and the flow-meter measurements (FLOW).

2.1 Uncertainty evaluation for the tilted-wave interferometer

In this implementation, a benchmark scenario is developed that applies the concepts of a simplified version of a tilted-wave interferometer (TWI) in a simple and numerically efficient way to define a VE. For that, a linearization of the TWI is considered that has been generated from analytical and numerical derivatives of the actual TWI simulation model. The combination of this linear simulation (or forward) model with a simple additive homoscedastic Gaussian noise assumption, provides the virtual experiment under consideration for this task. Subsequently, the uncertainty estimation methods, which were developed in A1.1.1 of this project, are implemented and applied for this specific virtual experiment and two different measurement models. Several cases are distinguished that consider different uncertainties of the selected input parameters. You will find further explanations in the code (MATLAB® Live-Script). The goal of this software is to implement and compare several methods for uncertainty evaluation of a linearized VE in conjunction with measurement data. Note that the results are not representative of the actual TWI and may differ significantly from uncertainties obtained in real experiments.

2.1.1 Where can I find the implementation?

The implementations for uncertainty evaluation methods that were developed for and applied to the simplified TWI application can be found in the software repository at the following path

```
vidit/WP1/Benchmark/TWI
```

2.1.2 What are the requirements?

The software is implemented in MATLAB® and was tested using version R2024b. The software requires no additional toolboxes, however, for parallel computation of some of the involved Monte Carlo simulations, the *MATLAB® Parallel computing toolbox* can be used.

2.1.3 Do I need additional data to run the implementation?

Yes, the linearization of the TWI is developed for a specific scenario and was extracted from the complex VE used in practice. The linearization must be stored in form of a Jacobian matrix for the software to run. For this, the DATA directory is already included in the full repository. When cloning the Gitlab repository, this

```
vidit/WP1/Benchmark/TWI/DATA
```

DATA directory must be included by the user. An in-depth description of the DATA that represents the numerical model for the linearized TWI can be found in the *DATA* directory, which also includes meta-data to ensure that the data is FAIR. In

particular, the **.mat* files in the *DATA* directory contain matrices and data structures that define the linearization of the forward model of the TWI for a specific choice of operation. These datasets can be exchanged for alternative linear models and is interoperable with the provided MATLAB® source code.

2.1.4 Where do I start?

Please refer to the *README* file first, available at
in the full Zenodo repository.

```
vidit/WP1/Benchmark/TWI/DATA/README.md
```

The actual implementations can be found in the MATLAB® live scripts

- `run_fwd_ve.mlx`
- `run_ucy_sota.mlx`
- `run_ucy_mcve.mlx`

that can be found in the appendix to this document and in the directory

```
vidit/WP1/Benchmark/TWI/
```

The first live script `run_fwd_ve.mlx` loads the VE from the dataset and generates virtual data from the linearized VE to use in the following data analysis. The second live script `run_ucy_sota.mlx` implements several state-of-the-art methods for uncertainty evaluation and discusses their usage for a linear model, motivated by the linearized TWI use-case. The final live script `run_ucy_mcve.mlx` implements the newly developed MCVE approach (Marschall, et al., 2024) (Hughes, et al., 2025), which applies a JCGM 101-compliant uncertainty evaluation that relies solely on evaluations of the VE. A collection of helper functions that provide functionality of loading and using the linearized VE, operating with 2D Zernike polynomials, plotting, and many more, can be found in the directory

```
vidit/WP1/Benchmark/TWI/HELPERS
```

2.2 Uncertainty evaluation for the coordinate measuring machine

The benchmark scenario of the coordinate measurement machine (CMM) includes a simplified version of a virtual CMM. The virtual CMM models the impact of the most relevant error sources on the measured coordinates of a 2D measurement. This includes the squareness error (between the x - and y -axis), two scale errors (one in x direction and one in the y direction), as well as Gaussian distributed random noise. The aim of the benchmarks scenario is to understand the differences between the different uncertainty estimation methods, as described in chapters 3 and 5 of D1. The benchmark scenario evaluates the uncertainty of the measurands (radius and roundness of a circular object) with the law of propagation of uncertainty (using either the data analysis function or the virtual experiment), propagation of distributions (either by applying perturbations to the measurement data, using the virtual experiment, or using the virtual experiment with bias corrections), and Bayesian inversion. In addition to studying the impact of the uncertainty evaluation methods on the uncertainty of the different measurands, the benchmark scenario also allows to study the differences of different data analysis methods, as the radius and roundness can be estimated with either least-squares or minimum zone optimization.

2.2.1 Location and access

The implementations for uncertainty evaluation methods that were developed for and apply to the TWI application can be found in the software repository at the following path

`vidit/WP1/Benchmark/CMM`

2.2.2 Programming language and requirements

The software is implemented in Python 3.10.11 and requires the following libraries (which can also be found in the file *requirements.txt*)

- numpy: 1.23.3
- pandas: 1.5.0
- scipy: 1.12.0
- matplotlib: 3.6.0
- emcee: 3.1.4
- openpyxl: 3.1.2

2.2.3 FAIR dataset

The CMM benchmark scenario is based on synthetic data which is generated at run-time. Therefore no datasets are required to use the CMM benchmark scenario. The settings do allow for automatic export of the settings, generated synthetic data, and output data. This allows for easy analysis and interpretation of the results, after using the CMM benchmark scenario.

2.2.4 Content and short description

Please refer to the *README* file first, available at

[vidit/WP1/Benchmark/CMM/README.md](#)

The CMM benchmark scenario can be used by running the file *example_use_case.py*. In this script, one can adjust which uncertainty evaluation methods are calculated, as well as which output is generated (and where the output is stored, if at all). In addition, the settings of the virtual CMM can be adjusted in *default_settings_CMM_benchmark.json*. This includes the mean and uncertainty of the measurands and error sources, as well as other settings regarding the measured objects (i.e. number of measured data points, form imperfections, etc.). More information regarding the different settings that can be defined by the user is available in the CMM benchmark documentation page, found at

[vidit/WP1/Benchmark/CMM/Documentation/index.html](#)

2.2.5 Examples

Some worked out examples regarding the usage of the CMM benchmark scenario are available in the CMM documentation page, found at

[vidit/WP1/Benchmark/CMM/Documentation/index.html](#)

The page “Basic usage” shows several examples on the use of the CMM benchmark scenario.

2.3 Uncertainty evaluation for the flow-meter measurements

In flow metrology, VEs are used to simulate how the flow measurement is influenced by disturbed flow conditions. For this, the entire physical system is modelled in a VE, applying the measurement principle to the calculated flow field. By comparing this virtually determined flow rate with the actual flow rate, an estimate of the fluid-mechanical calibration factor is provided. This fluid-mechanical calibration factor can then be used to correct the flow rate measurement under the considered disturbed flow conditions.

In order to apply the uncertainty evaluation methods defined in Section 3 of Deliverable D1 (ViDiT, D1 – Good practice guide on uncertainty evaluation for virtual experiments in conjunction with real measurements, 2026) to the virtual flow meter, the framework described in the publication “*A Novel Framework for Uncertainty Evaluation Applied to a Virtual Flow Meter*” (*Measurement Science and Technology*, DOI: 10.1088/1361-6501/adea0e) and in Section 6 of D1 (ViDiT, D1 – Good practice guide on uncertainty evaluation for virtual experiments in conjunction with real measurements, 2026) can be used.

The flow meter benchmark scenario (FLOW) consists of several case studies, which are described in detail in the publication “*A Novel Framework for Uncertainty Evaluation Applied to a Virtual Flow Meter*” (*Measurement Science and Technology*, DOI: 10.1088/1361-6501/adea0e). The aim of the benchmark scenario is to demonstrate the use of the implemented uncertainty evaluation methods for a specific flow application.

The corresponding software can be found at

WP1/Benchmark/FLOW

It enables the assessment of the following methods, which are described in more detail in D1 (ViDiT, D1 – Good practice guide on uncertainty evaluation for virtual experiments in conjunction with real measurements, 2026):

Method	Description
LPU-DA	Law of Propagation of Uncertainty using the Data Analysis (DA)
LPU-VEDA	Law of Propagation of Uncertainty using a Virtual Experiment-Data Analysis (VE-DA) combination
PoD-DA	Propagation of Distributions applied to DA
PoD-VEDA	Propagation of Distributions applied to VE, followed by DA

In the considered benchmark scenario, the methods use synthetic measurement data derived from a surrogate model. The surrogate model originates from “*A virtual flow meter downstream of various elbow configurations*” (*Metrologia*, DOI: 10.1088/1681-7575/ace7d6) and is available through the **FAIR Dataset**, which is stored in the `gui_data/` directory.

The baseline case used for all calculations is predefined directly in the main script (`main.py`) and can be modified by the user if desired. No external input data is required to run the FLOW benchmark scenario as all parameters are defined internally and synthetic data is generated at runtime. However, the results and settings can be exported for reproducibility and re-use.

2.3.1 Programming Language and Requirements

The software is implemented in Python 3.12 and requires the following main libraries:

- numpy
- pandas
- scipy
- matplotlib
- emcee
- openpyxl

These packages provide the necessary functionality for uncertainty propagation, data handling, statistical analysis and visualisation.

2.3.2 Content and Usage

Please refer to the *README* file for a detailed description of the repository structure and theoretical background at

WP1/Benchmark/FLOW/README.md

python main.py

The FLOW benchmark scenario can be executed by running:

Within this script, the user can:

- select which uncertainty evaluation methods to run (or all at once),
- adjust input quantities and their uncertainties,
- modify parameters of the flow meter setup (e.g., Reynolds number, pipe diameter, curvature radius, etc.),
- define where and how results should be stored.

The script automatically loads the **FAIR Dataset** based surrogate model from the `gui_data/` directory. The computed results are written as `.txt` files to the `results/`

folder.

2.3.3 Documentation and configuration

More information about the structure, model functions and mathematical details can be found in “A Novel Framework for Uncertainty Evaluation Applied to a Virtual Flow Meter” (Measurement Science and Technology, DOI: 10.1088/1361-6501/adea0e) and within the Gitlab documentation and in the source files. Source files contain:

- *model_functions.py*: defines forward and backward models for flow computations.
- *lpu_da.py*, *lpu_veda.py*, *pod_da.py*, *pod_veda.py*: contain the different uncertainty evaluation methods.
- *main.py*: defines the baseline case and executes the selected method(s).

2.3.4 FAIR Dataset

The surrogate model used for the FLOW benchmark scenario is based on a numerical model representing the fluid dynamic behaviour downstream of different elbow configurations / disturbances. This model forms the basis of the uncertainty assessment framework and complies with the FAIR data principles. The surrogate model data are included in the directory: *gui_data/*

This directory contains the precomputed data sets that make up the FAIR Dataset and are taken from the publication “A virtual flow meter downstream of various elbow configurations” (*Metrologia*, DOI: 10.1088/1681-7575/ace7d6).

The data represent a VE setup, which allows synthetic flow profiles to be generated at runtime without the need for experimental input data.

The *gui_data/* directory contains the following main components

- *FLOW_class_AW*- Surrogate model metadata and configuration.
- *FLOW_Meters/*- numerical data for various flow meter geometries.
- *FLOW_Profiles/*- simulated velocity and pressure field profiles for different elbow configurations.

When cloning the GitLab or GitHub repository, this directory must be included to ensure that the virtual FLOW model works correctly. The files define the surrogate model used by all uncertainty evaluation methods (LPU-DA, LPU-VEDA, PoD-DA, PoD-VEDA) implemented in the software.

The FAIR dataset can be exchanged with alternative surrogate models, provided they follow the same structural conventions. This interoperability allows users to apply the same uncertainty assessment framework to other flow configurations or measurement setups, supporting reproducibility and method benchmarking.

3 Software for uncertainty evaluation using digital twins

This part of the repository provides a set of examples of implementation of trustworthy digital twins (DTs) to different applications, with evidence of uncertainty evaluation.

3.1 Uncertainty evaluation for nanoindentation

This code contains functionality for the training and statistical testing of a nanoindentation testing machine DT for a specific combination of sample and indenter.

The DT is trained based on experimental measurements under nominal working conditions. Uncertainty estimation methods are applied to the mechanical characterization of the sample to create a virtual representation of the system under control.

Batches of experimental measurements can be tested through statistical tests to control the shape of the indentation curves and surface mechanical properties.

This code implements the methodology described in Section 3 of Deliverable D2 (ViDiT, D2 – Good practice guide on uncertainty evaluation for digital twins, 2026).

3.1.1 Location and Access

The implementations for uncertainty evaluation methods that were developed for

vidit/WP2/Nanoindentation

and apply to the TWI application can be found in the software repository at the following path

3.1.2 Programming language and requirements

The code is written in Python 3.11.9, using the additional packages listed below. For more information, please refer to the *README* file and the *requirements* file.

- numpy: 1.26.4
- matplotlib: 3.8.4
- scipy: 1.13.1
- tqdm: 4.66.4
- tabulate: 0.9.0

3.1.3 FAIR dataset

The DT of the nanoindentation is based on experimental data. FAIR dataset are

vidit/WP2/Nanoindentation/Datasets

provided at

Datasets are split in Train sets to model the DT, and *Test* sets. The Test sets is recommended to include at least 3 measurements (nanoindentation curves) to allow the control on the Indentation modulus reproducibility.

The experimental measurements provided with the code follows a predefined indentation cycle with secondary holding with the following durations:

- Loading: 10 s
- Primary Holding: 8 s
- Unloading: 10 s
- Secondary Holding: 60 s

A user defined input function may be needed, to load the experimental data from the machine specific file format to the `DT_Indentation_Curve` class used within the code.

3.1.4 Where do I start?

Please refer to the *README* file first, available at

```
vidit/WP2/Nanoindentation/code/README.md
```

Two main files are provided for the training of the DT and its use in statistical testing experimental curves, respectively.

```
vidit/WP2/Nanoindentation/code/DT_Training.py
vidit/WP2/Nanoindentation/code/DT_Test.py
```

- **DT_Training.py**: training of the DT based on the experimental curves provided in the specified `train_folder`. The code create and save the DT model of the system, a text log with mechanical properties and their uncertainty and graphical plots if requested by the user in the `# INPUTS` section
- **DT_Test.py**: experimental curves in the `test_folder` are tested against the DT model with 12 statistical tests to control the shape of the indentation curve, the thermal drift during the experiment and mechanical properties. Each rejected text is recorded in a text log file, listing the specific indentation not under control, type I error probability α , test p -value and type II error probability β .

Machine and sample specific `# INPUTS` and `# DEFINITIONS` (indenter area function parameters, machine frame compliance, indenter Young's Modulus, indenter and sample Poisson's ratio, ...) need to be defined in the upper parts of each file. Additional documentation regarding each variable is provided within the code, which is here summarized

DT TRAINING

A *train_folder* path shall be specified, containing the TXT files with the training indentations. Once machine-related parameters have been specified, i.e. area function parameters, the frame compliance and sample and indenter properties, the code trains the DT and outputs a model (*output_model_name*), a log file

```
vidit/WP2/Nanoindentation/Output/.../Output/train/
```

(*output_log*), and a train dataset (*output_train_dataset_name*). The outputs, in the FAIR datasets with examples are provided at

Indenter are function parameters can be either computed through a .tsv file (*indenter_calibration_file*, if *flag_indenter_fun_area_params* = False), or provided as hard-coded in terms of mean (*indenter_fun_area_params*) and covariance

vidit/WP2/Nanoindentation/Datasets/ReadMe_indenters.txt

(*indenter_fun_area_params_Cov*). For the FAIR Datasets, examples and information are available in the file

The frame compliance can be set in line #56 and #57; The poisson ratio and Young modulus of the indenter can be set in lines #64 to #68, the sample Poisson ratio in lines #61 and #62.

Care in separating the different phases of the indentation cycle should be paid, and related parameters should be set in lines #47 and #52.

DT TESTING

A DT trained model (*input_model_name*) and a reference dataset (*train_dataset_name*) shall be specified to test against a new indentations sets. Trained model and dataset are typically the output of the DT_Training.py.

Validation of the model can be performed by testing the trained model on the training datasets, and setting *phase* = 1. New data shall be tested against the reference model with *phase* = 2.

The test dataset path is specified in *test_folder* if real data are tested (*flag_pickle_dataset* = False). Synthetic data can also be tested (*flag_pickle_dataset* = True) and provided in a pickle file *pickle_dataset_name*.

DT_Test.py results are output in a log file (*output_log*) and via graphs, and stored in the path specified by (*output_log*).

The severity of the quality control can be set by the risk of error *alpha*.

Examples of Validation and Testing in the FAIR Datasets are at:

vidit/WP2/Nanoindentation/Output/.../Output/validation/
vidit/WP2/Nanoindentation/Output/.../Output/test/

3.2 Uncertainty evaluation for reference rotary table measurements

Location and access

The developed implementation for uncertainty evaluation of the Reference Rotary Table (LNE) is located in the ViDiT software repository under:

```
vidit/WP2/Reference rotary table/Virtual rotary table/
```

The corresponding dataset and MATLAB code are also archived on Zenodo under the identifier:

```
vidit-rotary-ve24-2025-10
```

(FAIR dataset prepared and documented according to D3).

Programming language and requirements

The software is implemented in MATLAB R2024b.

Optional toolboxes:

- Parallel Computing Toolbox (for Monte Carlo simulations).
- Signal Processing Toolbox (for filtering and spectral analysis).

Execution time: a few seconds on a standard workstation (Intel i7, 16 GB RAM).

FAIR dataset

The provided dataset and metadata describe a VE simulating the static behavior of a 24-face reference rotary table. The FAIR dataset includes:

- Code: code/rotary_ve_24faces.m
- Input resource: resources/wobble_cleaned.csv
- Generated data: data/processed/ve24_*.csv
- Metadata: metadata/rotary_ve24.yaml
- README documentation: README.md

Each dataset is assigned a persistent ID (vidit-rotary-ve24-2025-10) and complies with the FAIR principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

Content and usage

The MATLAB script implements a virtual rotary table simulating the metrological behavior of the LNE reference table in static mode ($\omega \approx 0$). It includes geometric, thermal, and encoder-related uncertainty sources:

- Geometric: eccentricity (T_x, T_y), tilt (R_x, R_y), axial (T_z).
- Thermal: global drift ($\Delta\theta_T = \alpha \Delta T$), gradient term ($A_{gradT} \cos(\theta - \phi_T)$).
- Encoder: interpolation ripple ($m = 8-32$), INL harmonics ($h = 4-12$).
- Noise and bias: Gaussian/Laplace mixture per sample, turn-level DC bias.
- Readout: scale ± 50 ppm, offset ~ 0.01 arcsec, optional latency shift.

To execute the VE:

```
run("code/rotary_ve_24faces.m");
```

The output datasets are written to `data/processed/` and can be used for uncertainty propagation and estimator validation (EKF/PF).

Examples and validation

The virtual experiment produces datasets that allow comparison between raw and corrected angle estimations. Validation results (1000 Monte Carlo runs):

Model Variant	Description	RMSE (°)
Raw measurement	No correction	0.00193
Mean-only	Temperature-averaged	0.00150
Thermal-only	Thermal correction only	0.00150
Static (Tx, Ty, Rx, Ry, α)	Geometric + thermal	0.00138
Dynamic (added latency, residuals)	Full model	0.00137

The observed improvement confirms that integrating geometric and thermal models enhances accuracy and repeatability.

Additional notes

==>Uncertainty evaluation: performed via GUM Monte Carlo and validated using residual analysis.

==> Estimator benchmarking: Extended and Particle Filters were tested for robustness against non-Gaussian noise.

Next version (v0.2): to include continuous rotation, latency modeling, and real sensor fusion (dual encoder + capacitive probes).

3.3 Uncertainty evaluation for optical machine-vision measurement

The developed software provides a conceptual digital twin demonstrator for optical machine-vision measurement, within the ViDiT project.

Its main objective is to estimate the measurement uncertainty of geometrical features (such as planes and spheres) based on configurable measurement parameters of a vision-based system.

The application represents a digital environment, allowing users to virtually reproduce a typical optical inspection scenario and evaluate the influence of robot positioning, calibration, and sensor parameters on the resulting uncertainty.

This work contributes to ViDiT's goal of ensuring traceable and reliable digital metrology tools for industrial applications.

Location and access

The software implementation developed by IDEKO for uncertainty evaluation in optical vision systems is available in the internal ViDiT software repository under the folder:

```
/ViDiT/WP2/DT Robotic Scanning
```

Detailed documentation, and the XML configuration file used by the application are included in the same directory.

Programming language and requirements

The application is developed in Python 3.8, using the following packages:

- tkinter - for the graphical user interface
- Pillow – for image and icon management

To install dependencies:

```
pip install Pillow  
pip install tkinter
```

Ensure that the following files are located in the same directory as the main script:

- data.xml – XML configuration file containing parameter sets for robot, calibration, and sensor options
- /logos/ – folder including logo1.png and custom_icon.ico

All files (main script, data.xml, and /logos/ folder) must be placed in the same directory.

When launched, the graphical interface opens in full-screen mode and allows the user to configure all parameters interactively.

How to use the software

After installation, the software can be used as follows:

1. **Launch the program**

Run the Python script (InterfaceEstimationUncertainty_v1.pypy). The GUI window opens automatically.

2. **Select configuration parameters**

- Choose a **robot**, **calibration**, and **sensor** from the dropdown menus.
- Optionally, edit numerical inputs for additional parameters related to the inspected surface (plane or sphere).

3. **Run uncertainty estimation**

- Click the **“Calculate”** button to perform the uncertainty estimation.
- The application computes the approximation of the combined uncertainty considering the selected parameters.

4. **View results**

- The resulting uncertainty value is displayed directly on the interface.
- Graphical feedback and textual outputs are provided for easy interpretation.

5. **Modify inputs and re-calculate**

- The user may explore multiple configurations to understand how each variable affects the overall measurement uncertainty.

6. **Close the application**

- The GUI can be closed directly from the interface or by pressing Esc.

All computations are performed instantaneously using uncertainty propagation models, allowing an evaluation of how system parameters contribute to the total uncertainty.

3.4 Uncertainty evaluation for electrical measurements

3.4.1 High voltage measurement

In this section, the essential information for using the software and data provided in the FAIR repository can be found. A complete manual is given and can be found as an Annex of this document.

THE SOFTWARE SPACS:

For the high voltage measurement application, the DT SPACS has been developed.

SPACS is a software program for the simulation of high voltage insulated power cable systems, which allows the calculation of currents and voltages induced by the sheaths of such cables. It is a program that allows the user to generate simulations through an easy-to-use graphical interface, unlike other simulation programs.

The program allows the simulation of different elements and different situations, enabling to configure a large number of parameters in order to adapt to the different real installations that can be modeled.

As VE, the program allows the optimal design of new transmission lines and the identification of possible faults in existing lines. As DT, the aim is to achieve an accurate calculation of the value of the induced voltages and currents on the sheaths. The DT software also includes the implementation of the Monte Carlo method for the uncertainty estimation of the results.

A complete manual explaining in detail how to use the user interface can be found as an annex, along with the instructions to use the software, a detailed case study is given.

USE OF REAL / SYNTHETIC DATA:

The user may choose to use synthetic data or real data. In Deliverable D3 (ViDiT, D3 – Report on the open access software repository including the implementation of the methods and FAIR data sets developed for the uncertainty evaluation of virtual experiments and digital twins, 2026), a test dataset is given, along with the instructions and software to generate synthetic data. At this point, in the software SPACS, for checking the results of the DT or for running the uncertainty estimation method implemented within the software, the user will select the data in the same way, being no difference between the synthetic and the real data.

REQUIREMENTS:

The only requirement is to install the required Matlab runtime. After this, the executable of the program is run with no further special requirements.

Optionally, the user might use some Matlab code for a better presentation of the results generated with the DT when running the Monte Carlo uncertainty estimation. To do so, Matlab is required. The scripts have been tested with the R2024b version of the program.

Further information can be found in the README file included in the repository.
A copy of said file is provided here:

```
REQUIREMENTS:

For the Matlab scripts, a compatible version of Matlab is required.

For the SPACS software, it is necessary to install the Matlab runtime
provided in the SPACS demo zip file. The program also needs several
files to work. It is recommended to decompress the folder and move
it to an appropriate location on your computer and execute the
software from there. No further installation is required.

#####

INSTALLATION:

1. Decompress zip folder (SPACS demo.zip)
2. Optionally, copy to desired location on your computer
3. Install Matlab runtime (executable file provided inside the zip
"MCRInstaller.exe")
4. Execute the .exe file (SPACS Version ViDiT 30-09-2025.exe). No
further installation is required

5. Once the Matlab runtime has been installed, the installation
wizard may be removed.

#####

NOTE:

For a detailed explanation on the contents of this folder, please
refer to the Deliverable D3 report.

The Matlab scripts have been programmed and tested with Matlab
R2024b.

For a detailed explanation on the use of the provided software,
please refer to Deliverable D4, section 3.5.1 and the related annex,
where a complete User Manual can be found.
```

DATASET STRUCTURE:

To facilitate the use of the scripts and the data provided, the nomenclature used in them is explained.

The data given is from a power line which endings are “*SubA*” and “*SubB*” (which stands for substations A and B respectively), which is composed of 15 sections, all with the sheath connected in cross-bonding. There are 4 intermediate grounded joints (which are named, starting from SubA, CE3, CE6, CE9 and CE12). In CE3, CE6 and CE9 joints there are sensor readings available.

For the currents, the name of each variable is structured in the following way:

For current readings:

For the voltage, the location is substituted by “Tensi_n”, as it is only measured in one point of the utility.

As for the temperatures, the nomenclature is as follows:

For temperature readings:

Except for the ambient temperature, which is only measured at CE3, and it is stored as “Temp_Nvz_CE3_Tamb”.

Other variables have been calculated using the previous data as a starting point. This include the power readings and the current through each sheath for each section. The nomenclature is summarized in the following chart.

For sheath currents:

For power:

SYNTHETIC DATA GENERATION:

The scripts available in the previous folder are:

1. Curve viewer: this script allows to plot the variables of interest to choose the days desired to use as entry for the interpolation of 24h-curves. It uses as entry the given test data file.
2. Curve treatment: this script allows to combine similar curves (by calculating the mean). It also allows to filter the curves, smoothing them, by performing the moving average. This script generates a *.mat file as output. It uses as entry the given test data file.
3. Curve interpolation: this script performs the interpolation between a given dataset of original curves. It uses as entry a folder containing multiple *.mat files generated by the curve treatment script.
4. Instant dataset active power: this script is provided with as many original data as possible to build a dataset that contains samples for a specified range of values of power and temperature. The script searches within the original data as many temperature-active power pairs as possible that meet the requirements established. Then, for the missing pairs, interpolation is used to complete them.
5. Instant dataset apparent power: its aim is the same as the one of the script number 4, but it uses the apparent power as the input variable for the interpolation. Again, this script is provided with as many original data as possible to build a dataset that contains samples for a specified range of values of power and temperature. The script searches within the original data as many temperature-apparent power pairs as possible that meet the requirements established. Then, for the missing pairs, interpolation is used to complete them.

To summarize the function of each of the previous scripts, and to facilitate its use, the flow chart shown in Figure 2 is given, where the workflow to expand the original dataset of 24h curves can be found.

Figure 2. Workflow for 24h synthetic data generation.

As for the instants dataset, it is only necessary to execute either the instant dataset for active power interpolation script (A04) or the instant dataset for apparent power interpolation script (A05).

Note that the original data file is the file provided in the FAIR dataset. It can be used for both datasets. In real scenarios, for the instant dataset it is recommended that a file with as many data as possible is given. In this way, the script can select as many registers as possible from the original data, reducing the need for interpolation, which improves the reliability of the dataset.

For using these scripts, the user must only fill the required variables (which are used for specifying the input files and other configurations), following the instructions given in the code comments.

3.4.2. Internal arc test

The software goal is to simulate internal arc faults in medium-voltage switchgear. In this simulation, two cases are developed that applies the concepts of simplified analytical modelling of arc-induced overpressure inside a switchgear and, if present, through a duct into the surrounding compartment. The simulation framework combines a set of analytical formulations (described in *D2, Section 6.2*) with user-defined geometrical, electrical, and thermodynamic input parameters.

To account for uncertainties, the software allows the user to specify probability distributions for critical input parameters such as ignition voltage and current, compartment volume, or discharge coefficients. These distributions are then propagated through the simulation model using a Monte Carlo approach, enabling the evaluation of resulting uncertainties in the pressure profiles. Several cases can be distinguished depending on the presence or absence of a duct, and on whether single- or three-phase arc faults are considered.

The goal of this software is therefore not only to simulate a single deterministic scenario, but also to implement and compare uncertainty propagation methods for internal arc simulations, providing a reliable framework for sensitivity analysis and robustness evaluation of different switchgear configurations in accordance with several standards.

The code is:

```
WP2/Internal Arc Test DT/IATOS.py
```

Project structure

Below are a breakdown of the main project files and the responsibilities of each component. The description also includes how the GUI maps to the computational workflow and how Monte Carlo runs are handled and exported.

IATOS.py — Main application

This script implements the graphical user interface (GUI) and organise the whole workflow from user input, through pre-processing, to execution and visualization.

a. Graphical interface

- Built with Tkinter and ttk.
- Organized as a tabbed interface (Notebook) with four main tabs: Test Configuration, Uncertainty Parameters, Simulation, and Results.

- The GUI includes input validation (numeric fields accept integers and decimals only), contextual tooltips/messages, and a progress indicator when simulations are running.

b. Tabs characteristics

- **Test Configuration (Tab 1)**

- i. Inputs include switchgear volume, presence/absence of duct, gas type (Air or SF₆), gas constants (R, γ), rupture pressure, hatch/ opening area and outlet conditions (density and pressure), compartment volumes, arc ignition timing (start/stop), and per-phase ignition voltages/currents.
- ii. If “has duct” is toggled on, additional fields for the duct compartment become enabled; otherwise, inputs are adapted to the two-compartment case (switchgear ↔ room). Default values are provided for quick testing.

- **Uncertainty Parameters (Tab 2)**

- i. For every relevant parameter the user can enable uncertainty and choose a distribution type (Normal or Uniform).
- ii. When a parameter is enabled, the user specifies the distribution parameters (mean & standard deviation for Normal; min & max for Uniform).
- iii. By default, the mean value is initialized from the values defined in Test Configuration and the deviation is set to 0.0 (i.e. no dispersion), making Monte Carlo optional and controlled.
- iv. The tab updates automatically whenever key values in Test Configuration change (phases, voltages, currents, volumes, etc.), keeping both tabs synchronized.

- **Simulation (Tab 3)**

- i. Shows a simple schematic of the selected configuration (with/without duct) and displays the main parameters in a compact panel.
- ii. The user performs a final check and presses Start Simulation.
- iii. Simulations run in a background thread, so the GUI stays responsive; a progress bar indicates activity.
- iv. If an exception occurs during simulation (input error, numerical failure), the progress bar is stopped, and a clear error dialog is shown — preventing the GUI from appearing frozen.

- **Results (Tab 4)**

- i. Numerical results (time series) and plots are shown using embedded Matplotlib canvases.
- ii. Typical outputs: Pressure vs Time, Temperature vs Time, and a histogram / distribution plot when Monte Carlo is used.
- iii. The tab provides export buttons to save numerical results (CSV) and figures as SVG (vector graphics) for publication-quality images.

c. Simulation

- The GUI builds the set of arguments required by the physical model and calls the simulation routine implemented in `arco_interno_analitico.py`.
- The initial condition dictionary is assembled dynamically depending on the topology (duct/no duct) and number of phases. This avoids code duplication (single generalized flow).

d. Monte Carlo

- If any input parameter in Tab 2 has an active distribution (i.e., arrays of values / nonzero dispersion), the application runs multiple realizations sampling those distributions and collects outputs for statistics.
- The number of Monte Carlo iterations is configurable from the GUI. (In the current configuration the example default used by the development team is 10^6 iterations — this number is configurable and can be increased if computational resources allow.)
- For each iteration the same simulation pipeline is invoked with the sampled inputs; final metrics (e.g., maximum compartment pressure, peak temperature) are stored, and summary statistics (mean, standard deviation) are computed and displayed.

Performance note: Large numbers of Monte Carlo iterations (e.g., 10^5 – 10^6) can be very time-consuming; the GUI is designed to keep the UI responsive and to give feedback via the progress bar, but the user should choose a number of iterations consistent with the available CPU time.

e. Visualization

- Matplotlib is embedded with FigureCanvasTkAgg. Plots are organized with `gridspec` to present multiple panels in the Results tab.
- The code stores the last simulation results in memory (`self.ultimos_resultados`) so the user can replot, zoom, or export without re-running the simulation.
- Exported SVGs preserve vector quality and are appropriate for inclusion in reports and publications.

f. Export

- The application can export:
 - i. Input distributions (CSV) used for Monte Carlo runs, with one CSV per input variable or a single combined file depending on the user preference.
 - ii. Output time series and summary statistics (CSV) with clear headers and units.
 - iii. Figures in SVG format (via `fig.savefig(..., format='svg')`) for high-quality images.
- Output directory is selectable via a standard file dialog.

Additional notes & best practices

- **Input validation:** Numeric entries validate keystrokes and prevent non-

numeric characters; when a field is left empty the application either enforces a default or warns the user, depending on the importance of the field. This prevents most simple user errors from crashing the simulation.

- **Error handling:** All numerical routines invoked from the GUI are executed in a worker thread and wrapped in try/except. On failure the GUI displays a clear error dialog and returns to a safe idle state. Tracebacks are logged to the console for debugging.
- **Extensibility:** The computational core (`arco_interno_analitico.py`) is modular and can be modified or extended with more detailed numerical models if needed, while keeping the same GUI front end.

This script contains the last version of the software. The uncertainty evaluation could be implemented inside the software, and it is possible to provide a simulation without uncertainty evaluation. Instead, the Monte Carlo method can be applied without the user interface. The code related to the uncertainty evaluation applying the Monte Carlo method execution, is provided in:

`WP2/Internal Arc Test DT/arco_interno_analitico.py`

`arco_interno_analitico.py` — Physical Model

This module contains the analytical core of the internal arc simulation. It provides a lightweight but physically representative description of gas expansion phenomena inside a medium-voltage switchgear during an internal arc fault, optionally connected to a duct and an external compartment.

a. Classes

The physical entities of the model are implemented through distinct classes, each encapsulating specific thermodynamic and geometric properties:

- **Tablero** — Represents the switchgear compartment, where the arc is ignited.
Contains parameters such as volume, rupture pressure, gas properties (specific gas constant R and heat capacity ratio γ), and heat transfer coefficient k_p .
- **Abertura** — Models an opening (e.g., pressure relief flap or duct connection) that allows gas to flow between compartments. Attributes include area, discharge coefficient, density, and upstream/downstream pressures.
- **Recinto** — Represents an adjacent compartment or room, typically the duct or surrounding environment, characterized by its own thermodynamic constants and volume.
- **Descarga_arco** — Describes the electric arc as a transient energy source. Defines ignition and extinction times, voltage and current profiles, and computes the corresponding power injection into the gas.

These classes are designed for modularity: users can extend or replace them (e.g., adding new types of outlets or arc models) without altering the rest of the framework.

b. Main Functions

The module provides several core functions that implement the governing equations and auxiliary calculations:

- **calculo_presion(time_Sim, init_cond, gases, Case, aberturas, recintos, arco, kp)**
Solves the system of coupled differential equations governing pressure, temperature, and mass flow evolution in the defined compartments.
The function integrates the physical balance equations — energy conservation, ideal-gas law, and mass exchange through openings — using adaptive time stepping.
It outputs time histories for pressures, temperatures, and flow variables ($p_1(t)$, $p_2(t)$, $T_1(t)$, etc.), which are later used for visualization and uncertainty propagation.
- **const_gases()**
Provides standard gas constants and thermodynamic reference data for air and SF₆, including temperature-dependent properties where relevant.
- **volt_corr_arco()**
Contains auxiliary relationships for arc voltage and current handling, useful for testing or defining parametric voltage-current dependencies.

Together, these routines allow the analytical resolution of simplified internal arc phenomena while maintaining physical consistency between energy release, gas expansion, and pressure equalization.

c. Property Tables

The module includes internally defined property tables and constant sets for the most used gases:

- **Air:** $R = 287 \text{ J}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$, $\gamma = 1.403$
- **SF₆:** $R = 52 \text{ J}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$, $\gamma = 1.094$

These constants are used as defaults but can be overwritten by user input through the GUI.

Temperature-dependent variants (for advanced testing) are also provided, ensuring consistency across deterministic and Monte Carlo simulations.

d. Usage outside the GUI

arco_interno_analitico.py can be imported and executed independently for research or automated testing. For instance, a Monte Carlo loop can be implemented directly in Python using:

```
from arco_interno_analitico import calculo_presion, Tablero, Abertura,
Recinto, Descarga_arco
```

allowing researchers to run high-volume simulations without the graphical interface.

This modular structure makes it straightforward to validate the analytical model, compare with experimental data, or embed the solver into other uncertainty

evaluation frameworks (e.g., SSPRC).

Detailed instructions on how to use the software for visualizing the results of the uncertainty evaluation are given in Section 3.5.2 of Deliverable D4 (ViDiT, D4 – User's guide for the software repository including well-documented examples and templates (e.g. Python notebooks) for the users to use and adapt, 2026). A brief description of is given in the README file located in

[WP2/Internal Arc Test DT/README.m d](#)

To run the software, make sure you have Python 3, Tkinter, NumPy, and Matplotlib installed. Open a CMD terminal in the same directory as IATOS.py and run it using the Python interpreter. The program should start in a new window.

Two reference test cases are provided in the data linked below

[WP2/Internal Arc Test DT/data/cases.xlsx](#)

The dataset contains all the necessary configuration input parameters to reproduce the benchmark simulations and verify the performance of the software, with and without duct. In figures Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5, shows the configuration and results of case A from the data linked.

IATOSv1.0 - Internal Arc Test Overpressure Simulator

Welcome | 1. Test Configuration | 2. Uncertainty Parameters | 3. Simulation | 4. Results

Metal-enclosed switchgear parameters

Switchgear volume [m³]:

The switchgear has duct?

Type of gas in switchgear:

- Air
- SF₆

Specific gas constant R [J/kg·K]: 287

Heat capacity γ [adimensional]: 1.403

Initial pressure [Pa]:

Rupture pressure [Pa]:

Electric arc parameters

Ignition time [s]: Shutdown time [s]:

Phases: 1 phase 3 phases

Voltage [V]: Current [A]:

Heat transfer coefficient [adimensional]:

Hatch parameters

Area [m²]:

Air density at exit [kg/m³]:

Discharge coefficient [adimensional]:

Pressure at exit [Pa]:

Figure 3. Test configuration tab with case A parameters.

Figure 4. Results tab of case A with pressure evolution and maximum pressure inside switchgear compartment without uncertainty analysis.

IATOSv1.0 - Internal Arc Test Overpressure Simulator

Welcome 1. Test Configuration 2. Uncertainty Parameters 3. Simulation 4. Results

Uncertainty for Input Parameters

Variable: Voltage phase R

Activate Distribution: Normal

Mean: 314.0 Std. deviation: 3.14

Variable: Current phase R

Activate Distribution: Normal

Mean: 14500.0 Std. deviation: 145

Variable: Volume switchgear compartment

Activate Distribution: Normal

Mean: 0.509 Std. deviation: 0.0

Variable: Temperature switchgear compartment

Activate Distribution: Normal

Mean: 300 Std. deviation: 0.0

Variable: Temperature compartment at exit

Activate Distribution: Normal

Mean: 300 Std. deviation: 0.0

Variable: Pressure switchgear compartment

Activate Distribution: Normal

Mean: 150000.0 Std. deviation: 0.0

Variable: Discharge coefficient

Activate Distribution: Uniform

Mean: 0.65 Width: 0.15

Variable: Heat transfer coefficient

Activate Distribution: Uniform

Mean: 0.4 Width: 0.1

Show configuration

Figure 5. Uncertainty parameters tab for uncertainty analysis. Both, arc voltage and current are set with 1% uncertainty with a normal distribution. For the discharge coefficient and heat transfer coefficient a uniform distribution was set.

Figure 6. Results tab of case A with pressure evolution and maximum pressure inside switchgear compartment with uncertainty analysis.

3.4.3. Quantum voltage standard

The goal of the quantum voltage standard DT software is to develop a model of the physical system that makes predictions of its behavior with uncertainty quantification. The code prepares the data for dataset creation, trains a sequence-to-sequence Mixture Density Network (the model of the DT), and then makes predictions with uncertainty quantification using GUM Monte Carlo for input uncertainty propagation and Monte Carlo Dropout for the model's uncertainty. It produces multi-step forecasts with decomposed uncertainty (aleatoric, epistemic, and input-induced). Finally, it plots the results comparing predictions with test data. The code implements the methodology depicted in Section 6.3 of Deliverable D2 (ViDiT, D2 – Good practice guide on uncertainty evaluation for digital twins, 2026).

The software can be found at:

[vidit/WP2/Quantum Voltage Standard DT](#)

The code is programmed in Python, using the additional packages listed below. For more information, please refer to the README file and the requirements file.

Quick start

From the repository root:

```
# create a Python venv (recommended)
```

```
python -m venv .venv
```

```
source .venv/bin/activate # Linux / macOS
```

```
# .venv\Scripts\activate # Windows (PowerShell: .venv\Scripts\Activate.ps1)
```

```
# install minimal dependencies
```

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

```
# prepare the data (reads raw file under data/)
```

```
python scripts/prepare_data.py
```

```
# train the model (uses the prepared + scaled data)
```

```
python scripts/train_model.py
```

```
# run uncertainty calculations and example plot
```

```
python scripts/calc_uncertainty.py
```

Prerequisites:

- Python 3.9+ recommended
- pip
- GPU recommended for training, but CPU will work (training and Monte Carlo sampling may be slow on CPU)
- Disk: able to store data/ outputs (model + npz files)

Required Python packages:

- numpy>=1.21.0
- tensorflow>=2.10.0
- keras>=2.10.0
- scikit-learn>=1.1.0
- matplotlib>=3.5.0
- joblib>=1.1.0

Installation

1. Clone the repository:

```
git clone https://gitlab1.ptb.de/vidit-group/vidit/-/tree/main/WP2/Quantum%20Voltage%20Standard%20DT
```

```
cd Quantum Voltage Standard DT
```

2. Create and activate a virtual environment (recommended):

```
python -m venv .venv
```

```
source .venv/bin/activate
```

3. Install dependencies:

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

The FAIR dataset (DC_1V_100000pts_25 μ sAper_20kSs.txt) contains the raw voltage values of a DC measurement of 1 V, performed with TÜBITAK UME PJVS system. The software processes this data to match the model inputs. Dataset and all the files generated by the code are in

```
vidit/WP2/Quantum Voltage Standard DT/data
```

How to run

Software is divided into three applications:

1. Data preparation (scripts/prepare_data.py): takes the raw voltage from the measurements and processes this time-series data to build sequence-to-sequence sets, splits them into training/validation/test datasets, and scales the data so it's ready to use to train the model. It saves the scalers and datasets for future use.

Purpose:

- Load raw 1-D time series voltage file from data/
- Build sliding-window seq2seq examples (X, Y)
- Split into train/val/test (70/20/10)
- Fit and save StandardScaler for X and Y
- Save raw and scaled datasets as npz

Outputs:

- data/dataset_raw.npz (raw sequences)
- data/dataset_scaled.npz (scaled sequences ready for training)
- data/scaler_X.pkl and data/scaler_Y.pkl (joblib scalers)

Key parameters:

- file — raw filename in data/
 - T_in — input window length
 - T_out — output horizon
 - stride — sliding step
 - Random seed via set_seed(...)
2. Model training (train_model.py): loads the scaled training/validation datasets, builds and trains the Mixture Density Network model (with MC-Dropout for epistemic uncertainty), then saves the trained model and its parameters.

Purpose:

- Load scaled training/validation sets
- Build MDN model (Conv1D → Dense → MDN heads)
- Compile with custom MDN loss & mixture MAE metric
- Train with early stopping + LR reduction
- Save trained model and append training metadata to data/parameters.json

Outputs:

- data/QVS_DT.keras — saved Keras model
- Appended entry in data/parameters.json with training metadata

Key parameters:

- layer_neurons — list of dense layer sizes (e.g. [512,256,128,64])
- dropout — dropout rate (MC dropout)
- K_comp — number of Gaussian components for the MDN
- epochs, batch_size, early_stopping_patience, reduceLR params

Note:

- The script sets `tf.keras.backend.set_floatx('float64')` for higher numeric precision. If your environment or GPU drivers don't support float64 efficiently, you can change/remove that line but results/uncertainty will differ.
3. Uncertainty calculation (`calc_uncertainty.py`): loads the trained model, calculates predictive mean and decomposed uncertainty (aleatoric, epistemic, input-induced) using GUM Monte Carlo input propagation with MC-Dropout. It saves the results and parameters/metrics and plots an example of a single prediction with measurement uncertainty.

Purpose:

- Load raw test inputs and trained model + scalers
- Run GUM Monte Carlo (input perturbations) combined with MC-Dropout to estimate total predictive uncertainty decomposed into:
 - Aleatoric (inherent noise learned by MDN)
 - Epistemic (model uncertainty via MC-Dropout)
 - Input-induced (propagation of input measurement uncertainty)
- Save data/uncertainty.npz and append summary to data/parameters.json
- Plot a single example prediction with measurement uncertainty bars

Outputs:

- data/uncertainty.npz — contains `mu_raw`, `sigma_raw`, and components:

aleatoric_var, epistemic_var, input_var, total_var

- Appended entry in data/parameters.json with RMSE/MAE and run parameters

Key parameters:

- K_mc — number of MC-Dropout forward passes (e.g., 50)
- M_in — number of input perturbations per test sample (GUM) (e.g., 50)
- u_X — input measurement standard uncertainty (in raw volts)
- K_comp and T_out must match the trained model's config

Note:

- The combined batch size sent to the model in the uncertainty step is $M_{in} * K_{mc}$. If $M_{in}=50$ and $K_{mc}=50$, that's 2500 forward passes batched at once per test sample — memory can blow up. If you get OOM, reduce M_{in} or K_{mc} , or modify the code to process in smaller chunks.

These applications are in

```
vidit/WP2/Quantum Voltage Standard DT/scripts
```

A detailed explanation of how the code works and how to run it can be found in the README.md file, located in

```
vidit/WP2/Quantum Voltage Standard DT/README.md
```

Troubleshooting

- Out of memory on calc_uncertainty.py
Lower M_{in} and/or K_{mc} . For example, $M_{in}=10$, $K_{mc}=10$ is much lighter. You can also modify uncertainty_utils.gum_mc_propagation_mc_dropout to process smaller batches of $M_{in} * K_{mc}$ at a time (this adds runtime but reduces memory footprint).
- Training is slow
Use a GPU if available. Set TF GPU memory growth to avoid OOM:

```
gpus = tf.config.list_physical_devices('GPU')
```

```
if gpus:
```

```
tf.config.experimental.set_memory_growth(gpus[0], True)
```

Reduce layer_neurons, epochs, or increase batch_size (careful: batch_size interacts with numeric precision).
- Precision (float64)
The repo sets TF default float type to float64. If your TF installation or GPU drivers don't support float64 efficiently, consider switching to float32 (change set_floatx('float64')). Ensure consistency across scripts and scalars if you change precision.
- Model not found

If `calc_uncertainty.py` cannot find `data/QVS_DT.keras`, run `train_model.py` first or set `model_path` to the correct model file.

- Versions & reproducibility

Pin package versions in `requirements.txt` for reproducible runs. Save `data/parameters.json` outputs for run auditing.

- Custom raw file / different sampling

If you use a different raw file or different sampling rate, adjust `file`, `T_in`, `T_out`, and `stride` accordingly in `prepare_data.py`.

Reproducibility notes

- Each script sets a random seed via `src.data_utils.set_seed(seed)` for reproducibility. However, full bitwise reproducibility depends on:
 - Deterministic TF ops (`TF_DETERMINISTIC_OPS=1` helps)
 - Exact TensorFlow, CUDA, cuDNN, and NumPy versions
 - Single-threaded operation (the code sets TF threading to 1 in `set_seed`) Save the `data/parameters.json` entries and package versions used to help reproduce an exact run.

Run example

The results using the default values `K_mc = 50` (MC dropout) and `M_in = 50` (input perturbations) are shown below:

Figure 7. Results of predictions with uncertainty quantification for `K_mc = 50` and `M_in = 50`.

If you want a quick, low-memory uncertainty estimation before committing large runs, edit `scripts/calc_uncertainty.py`:

```
K_mc = 10 # smaller MC dropout
```

$M_{in} = 10$ # fewer input perturbations

This reduces memory by (factor ≈ 25) compared with 50×50 .

4 References

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1 ANNEX – SPACS – SOFTWARE FOR HIGH VOLTAGE APPLICATION

1.1 Introduction

SPACS is a software program for the simulation of high voltage insulated power cable systems, which allows the calculation of currents and voltages induced by the sheaths of such cables. It is a program that allows the user to generate simulations through an easy-to-use graphical interface, unlike other simulation programs.

The program allows the simulation of different elements and different situations, enabling to configure a large number of parameters in order to adapt to the different real installations that can be modeled.

As VE, the program allows the optimal design of new transmission lines and the identification of possible faults in existing lines. As DT, the aim is to achieve an accurate calculation of the value of the induced voltages and currents on the sheaths. The DT software also includes the implementation of the Monte Carlo method for the uncertainty estimation of the results.

1.2 Interface

One of the advantages of SPACS over other cable system simulation programs is its ease of use. It has an intuitive and user-friendly interface. The following is a detailed explanation of how to model a transmission line, including an example of a 220 kV line, with a middle cross bonding section and two single point sections at the ends.

Figure 8. SPACS interface with the example line and a single-phase ground fault.

1.3 Main toolbar

The main toolbar provides quick access to the different operations that can be performed on a circuit in the worksheet.

Figure 9. Main toolbar

The components of the main toolbar are, from left to right: (hotkeys are shown in brackets).

New project (Ctrl + N): Create a new project.

Open project (Ctrl + O): Open an existing project.

Save project (Ctrl + S): Save the current project.

Save project as (Ctrl + H): Save the current project for the first time. Allows you to save an existing project by choosing a new name and location.

Print project (Ctrl + P): Creates a disk file in Enhanced Metafile (.emf) format.

Undo: undoes the previous operation.

Redo: repeats the previous operation.

Zoom + (F1): Increases the display size of the circuit in the worksheet.

Zoom - (F2): Decreases the display size of the circuit in the worksheet.

Drag: When activated, allows you to move the entire worksheet. If it is activated, when the pointer enters the worksheet, the shape of the pointer changes from an arrow ()), and move the mouse to move the sheet to the desired position. Once moved, uncheck the box to disable this option and perform a different operation.

Redraw (Ctrl + R): This command redraws all objects on the active circuit worksheet.

Adjust outline schematic: Automatically adjusts the size of the circuit to the worksheet.

Move circuit: When activated, it allows you to move the entire circuit within the workspace. Once activated, click on the circuit to be moved. The circuit is selected and the shape of the pointer changes from an arrow () allowing to move the circuit to the desired position. Clicking again removes the selection of the circuit. Once it has been moved, the check box must be unchecked to deactivate this option and perform a different operation.

Insert text (Ctrl +T): Allows you to insert text into the worksheet. To do this, click on the icon and click on the area of the worksheet where you want to insert the text. Once this is done, a text window is inserted in the worksheet with the following default text: *“INSERT TEXT”*. To modify the text content, double-click on the text window. Right-clicking inside the text window displays a drop-down menu with typical Windows editing options (copy, cut, paste, delete and select all).

General Options: Opens the *“Default General Options”* menu.

System voltage: Allows to modify the system voltage of the worksheet circuit. Initially, it shows the default voltage that appears in General Options. Additionally, it indicates the number of sections that make up the current worksheet circuit.

Calculate (F5): Runs the simulation, calculating the voltages and currents of the circuit. These parameters are displayed in the circuit. At the same time, it creates the output files with the simulation results. These files are created in the directory where the project file is saved. Before simulating, it is necessary to save the project to a file.

Display absolute voltages: Once the circuit simulation has been run, it displays the absolute voltages on the cable sheaths for each accessory of the circuit.

Show local voltages: Once the circuit simulation has been executed, it shows the local voltages on the cable sheaths for each accessory of the circuit.

Show currents: Once the circuit simulation has been executed, it displays the current flow through the cable sheaths for each cable section (except for single point sections), the current flow through the equipotential cables (if any) and the current distribution through ground.

1.4 Creating a new circuit

Once the program has been opened, the first thing to do is to select the system voltage. To do this, click on the *General Options* icon and in the pop-up window select the desired system voltage under *System voltage*, which in the example case is 220 kV. To model a circuit, you must always start by creating a section. The rest of the circuit is created upon this section. The first section can be any of the sections that make up the circuit, since other elements can then be connected to this section from either end. Voltage sources cannot be inserted until at least one section is present.

1.4.1 Inserting and configuring underground cables and overhead line sections

To insert cable or line sections, right-click on any blank space in the worksheet. When doing so, the component menu appears, where you can select the kind of section you want to insert through the submenus that appear.

Figure 10. Selection of a circuit section

When selecting the desired element, the mouse icon changes from arrow () and, by clicking on the worksheet, it is possible to add the selected component in the desired location.

With the Zoom In, Zoom Out and Drag buttons, you can change the location of the circuit on the worksheet. With the Adjust Schematic button, you can center the circuit as it is being created. The mouse wheel is used to move the circuit vertically.

All sections are created with the default settings that appear in the submenus *Default wire configuration* and *Default line configuration*.

Once a section has been entered, the settings can be modified with the desired data for each section.

1.4.2 Types of section

In the following table the types of sections that can be entered are shown, with a brief description for each of them. In addition, the display of the section in SPACS is shown.

SECTION	TYPE SECTION	DESCRIPTION	SPACS IMAGE
CROSS-BONDING	Cross-Bonding Sectioned	Cross-Bonding composed of three (3) subsections and no accompanying cable. The number of subsections cannot be chosen. If it is desired to model a Cross-Bonding with a larger number of subsections, the <i>Continuous Cross-Bonding</i> section must be selected.	
	Cross-Bonding Sectioning with accompanying cable	Cross-Bonding formed by three (3) subsections and with an accompanying cable along the section.	
	Continuous Cross-Bonding	Cross-Bonding composed of a number of subsections chosen by the user and with accompanying cable along the section.	
	Continuous Cross-Bonding with accompanying cable	Cross-Bonding formed by a number of subsections chosen by the user and with accompanying cable along the section.	

SINGLE-POINT	LTP in the left ending (SPI)	Single-Point section with overvoltage limiters on the left side of the section and equipotential cable along the section.	
	LTP in the right ending (SPD)	Single-Point section with overvoltage limiters on the right-side of the section and equipotential cable along the section.	
SOLID-BONDING	Solid-Bonding	Solid-Bonding Section	
Overhead Line	Overhead Line	Line section with guard cable(s).	

Table 1

To start modelling the example circuit, start by inserting the *Cross-Bonding* section. Right-click on the worksheet, select *Major Section -> Cross bonding -> Sectionalized* from the component menu. Then click on any point on the worksheet.

Figure 11. Inserting the first section of a circuit.

Once the first section has been inserted, there are two ways to insert the next one:

Right-click on the section, the section editing menu appears, and select *Insert right* or *Insert left*, depending on which side you want to insert the new section. This displays a new component menu, where you can choose the new section. Once selected, the new section is automatically inserted into the circuit.

In the example case, the Single Point section with LTP is inserted to the left of the Cross-Bonding section.

Figure 12. Concatenate a new section to the left of an existing section.

The second way to insert a section is to right click on a blank space on the worksheet and then select the new section to be inserted from the components menu. The pointer changes from arrow (↔) to a cross (+). To connect the new section to the circuit, click near the end of the existing section to which you want to connect the new section.

Figure 13. Concatenate a new section to the right of an existing section.

1.4.3 Voltage sources

To insert a voltage source, select *Voltage Source* in the components submenu and then select the desired type of source depending on the grounding. To be able to insert a voltage source into a circuit, there must be at least one section already inserted.

TYPE OF VOLTAGE SOURCE	DESCRIPTION	IMAGE SPACS
<p>Voltage source with reference to substation ground</p>	<p>The grounding of the substation is connected to the grounding of the cable sheaths that are connected to the substation.</p>	<p>NOMBRE DE S/E: 220 kV</p>

<p>Voltage source with far earth reference</p>	<p>The grounding of the substation is independent of the grounding of the cable sheaths that are connected to the substation.</p>	<p>NOMBRE DE S/E: 220 kV</p>
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Table 2. Voltage sources in SPACS.

Right-click on the worksheet and select *Voltage Source* from the component menu.

Figure 14. Selection of a voltage source.

Figure 15. Insert voltage source(s).

1.5 Configure sections

Once the necessary sections have been inserted, they have to be configured with the

project specifications. To configure the sections, the section properties editing window must be opened. There are three ways to open the editing window.

- Double click on the section.
- Right-click. This opens a drop-down menu with the options for editing the section. Select *Edit Properties and click*.
- Click on the section and then press the *Space* key.

When you perform one of these three operations, a new window opens, where you can modify the data of the different sections you have entered.

When an editing window is opened, no changes can be made to the circuit until the window is closed.

1.5.1 Modification of underground section data

Once the data editing window of an underground section is open, we can configure the section according to our design data.

Important: It is highly recommended to refresh the data displayed by default when an underground section is entered, although in some cases the values that the user wishes to select may appear. To do this, in the *'Cable system voltage'* field, open the drop-down menu and select the desired voltage. This will refresh all the fields. Once refreshed, the user will choose the desired parameters.

Figure 16. Underground section data editing window.

Header of the editing window: Shows information about the section. It has the following structure: Circuit 'N'. Section data 'M' (Section Type).

- **Circuit 'N':** Indicates the circuit to which the section belongs (in the example in Figure 16, the section belongs to circuit 1).
- **Section 1 data.** The program numbers the sections in increasing order from left to right. As more sections are introduced, the program renumbers all the sections that exist in the circuit (in the example in Figure 16 is the first section).
- **Section Type:** This indicates the type of section to which the open editing window belongs (in the example in Figure 16 it is a Cross-Bonding section).

Subsection: For cross-bonding sections, it indicates the subsection of the cross-bonding in which we are. Once subsection 1 has been configured, select subsection 2 to configure it, and so on with all the existing subsections. For Single-Point and Solid-Bonding sections there is only one subsection.

Stretch: For each subsection, you can add as many stretches as you need to represent changes in the topology of the installation. Once Stretch 1 has been configured, it is necessary to select Stretch 2 to configure it, and so on with all the existing stretches for each of the subsections of the section. The program performs the joining of stretches as an ideal joining of conductors.

To add or remove spans, click on the *Add Span and Remove Span* buttons respectively.

Cable system voltage: Shows the cable system voltage. It does not represent a calculation voltage, but rather, for each voltage, it loads the elements (cables, types of installation, etc.) from the internal database corresponding to that voltage level. In other words, even if the system voltage defined by the user at the start of the circuit is for example 132 kV, a different cable system voltage can be chosen (for example 220 kV) to configure the section with insulation of a voltage different from the calculation voltage.

Soil resistivity (ρ_{soil}): For each Span, it allows to select a soil resistivity value.

Type of installation: Allows you to choose the type of installation of the cables in the ground (in a trench, in a gallery, etc.).

Configuration: Allows you to choose the disposition of the conductors in the installation (staggered or layered).

Designation: Depending on the type of installation and the chosen configuration, it allows a particular disposition to be chosen from those available in the database (this determines the coordinates of the conductors in the terrain).

Cable: Allows you to select a power cable from those available in the database.

Accompanying cable: Allows you to select an accompanying cable from those available in the database. This option is only available when the section that has been entered has an accompanying wire (Cross-Bonding sections with accompanying wire or Single-Point sections).

Transposition point: Allows you to select the point where you want to represent the transposition of the accompanying cable. It is chosen as a percentage of the total length of the section, taking as origin the beginning of the section (left side of the corresponding section). If you do not want to transpose the cable, select 0% or 100% (0% means that only equipotential 2 exists, 100% means that only equipotential 1 exists). This option is only available if the section entered has an accompanying cable (Cross-Bonding sections with accompanying cable or Single-Point sections).

Double Accompaniment Cable: For sections that have an accompaniment cable (Cross-Bonding sections with accompaniment cable or Single-Point sections), this option allows the addition of a second accompaniment cable. The second accompanying wire will be the same as the existing one and is chosen in *Accompanying Cable*.

Length: Length of each stretch of the subsection, in meters.

Continuous Junction: When more than one span is added to a subsection, when this

option is selected, the letters EC (Continuous Junction) are represented in the section image, to differentiate from a junction of spans that represents a change in the circuit topology.

Once you have modified all the stretches, and all the desired sub-sections, click on the *OK* button to save the changes.

1.6 Steady state study. Study of loaded power lines.

SPACS allows studies to be carried out in steady state, by simulating the circuit under load. The load is a balanced three-phase impedance, connected in star. To enter the three-phase charge, right-click on a blank space on the worksheet and select *Miscellaneous* -> *Three Phase Load* from the component menu. The mouse icon changes from arrow (). To connect the load to the circuit, click near the end of the section where you want to connect the load.

Figure 17. Selection of a three-phase load.

To modify the impedance value of each of the phases, you must double click on the three-phase load and modify the data that appears in the pop-up window. The data

must be entered in binomial form as follows:

$$a + jb$$

Figure 18. Modification of the impedance values of a three-phase load.

1.7 Study in time-domain analysis. Short-circuits in power lines.

SPACS allows time-domain analysis, by simulating different short-circuits in the circuit. To enter a fault, right-click on a blank space on the worksheet, select *Fault* from the components menu, and then select the type of fault you wish to enter from the options shown. Once the type of fault has been selected, the mouse icon changes from arrow (↔) to cross (+). To connect the fault to the circuit, click on the part of the circuit where the short-circuit is to be made.

Figure 19. Selecting a fault.

The types of faults available are shown in the following table:

FAULT TYPES	POSITION	IMAGE SPACS
THREE-PHASE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Substation. • Extremities of underground sections. 	
SINGLE-PHASE TO LOCAL GROUNDING	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Substation. • Extremities of underground sections. 	

<p>SINGLE-PHASE TO GROUND</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Substation. • Extremities of underground sections. 	
<p>SINGLE-PHASE INTERNAL TO THE CABLE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Along underground sections. 	
<p>DUE TO THE FALL OF THE LEFT CONDUCTOR ON AN OVERHEAD LINE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On any transmission tower 	
<p>DUE TO THE FALL OF THE RIGHT CONDUCTOR ON AN OVERHEAD LINE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On any transmission tower 	
<p>BY REVERSE PRIMING ON AN OVERHEAD LINE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In any span of the overhead power line. 	

Table 3. Fault types.

1.8 Results of the study

Once a fault or a three-phase load has been introduced, to solve the circuit and obtain the results, the circuit must be simulated. To do this, click on the *Calculate* icon on the main toolbar, or press the F5 key. The program performs the simulation, providing the voltages and currents. To be able to run the simulation, the file must first be saved.

Figure 20. Icon “Calculate”. Allows to simulate the case study.

Once a case study has been executed, the program calculates the voltages on the cable sheaths and in the sheaths of all the accessories of the line. It also calculates the currents on every part of the circuit. The results obtained are:

- Absolute sheath voltages (U_{abs}) of all accessories. They correspond to values referred to a ground remote and are the voltages to which the enclosures are requested.
- Local sheath voltages (U_{loc}) of all accessories fitted with overvoltage limiters. They correspond to the voltage values seen by the overvoltage limiters.
- Grounding voltages. These correspond to the voltage values at the grounding points of accessories and supports. (This result is only shown in the numerical output generated by SPACS)
- Currents (I). Shows the currents by each part of the circuit.
 - Short-circuit current and current supplied by the substations, when a simulation is run with a fault in the circuit.
 - Load current and contributed by the substations, when a simulation is run with a three-phase load in the circuit.
 - Currents through the cable sheaths and equipotential cables.
 - Currents through the ground connections.

SPACS shows the calculated results on the circuit by clicking on the Show icons in the toolbar. When the *Show* icons are activated, they are displayed on the circuit, and when the icons are deactivated, they are hidden.

Figure 21. Activated “Show” icons. They allow the simulation results to be displayed.

By default, when running a simulation, SPACS shows the absolute voltages of the sheaths.

Figure 22. Detail of absolute voltages at all line accessories due to a single-phase local ground fault at junction E5.

Figure 23. Detail of local voltages at all power line accessories fitted with voltage limiters due to a single-phase local ground fault at junction E5.

Figure 24. Detail of the distribution of currents in the circuit due to a single-phase local ground fault in the substation.

Finally, to represent the transmission line right, it is necessary to introduce the cable distribution. The default value once the user is selecting the cable section is the staggered arrangement. If the modification of the distance in between the cables is required, the user can select the “View” (“Ver”) option, shown in Figure 24. By doing this, a window like the one shown in Figure 24 opens, allowing the user to view the current layout of the cables.

Figure 25. Section menu

Figure 26. "View" menu

By clicking on one of the cables, the values of its center coordinates X and Y can be modified. In Figure 26, Phase 4 is selected to illustrate the effects of varying these parameters:

1.8.1 Use case

A real power line is modelled in SPACS. It is a fully underground line, of 220 kV and capable of transporting 470 MVA. Its sheaths are connected following the cross-bonding configuration. This power line connects two substations, named SubA and SubB. The electrical power flow is bidirectional, but for this given example SubA is modelled as the power source and the second substation, SubB, is modelled as the load.

Cable specifications

The cable used in this power line has a 2000 mm² copper section for the active conductor. Its sheath is made of 315 mm² copper wires. The cable's insulation is cross-linked polyethylene (XLPE) and its outer sheath is made from polyethylene (PE). The length of each section and its denomination is given in Table 4.

Minor section	Initial joint	End joint	Length (m)	Major section
1	SubA	CE1	412,42	SubA-CE3
2	CE1	CE2	418,59	
3	CE2	CE3	417,07	
4	CE3	CE4	680,54	CE3-CE6
5	CE4	CE5	692,75	
6	CE5	CE6	679,72	

7	CE6	CE7	662,93	CE6-CE9
8	CE7	CE8	662,92	
9	CE8	CE9	634,62	
10	CE9	CE10	668,14	CE9-CE12
11	CE10	CE11	667,90	
12	CE11	CE12	667,42	
13	CE12	CE13	438,21	CE12-SubB
14	CE13	CE14	466,60	
15	CE14	SubB	464,06	

Table 4. Power line specifications.

Firstly, to model the power line, the mayor sections must be introduced. To do so, the following components are selected from the “interface” section:

TYPE SECTION	SOURCE	LOAD
Cross-Bonding Sectioned	Voltage source with far earth reference	

Table 5. Selected components from “interface” section.

The sheaths are interconnected following the “480” sequence. The cables are positioned in a staggered arrangement, and the length of each minor section is obtained from the project specifications. The previous data must be introduced in the menu that has been shown in Figure 16.

With the prior configuration and having modelled SubA as the generator and SubB as the electrical load, the SPACS model is now fully established.

Figure 27. Final configuration.

By clicking the “Calculate” icon (see Figure 20) and by using the “Show” icons (see Figure 21) the DT returns the data shown in Table 6:

Table 6. SPACS results.

The results given by the DT can be compared against real data from an example power line, which is given in the FAIR dataset, as described in Deliverable D3 (ViDiT, D3 – Report on the open access software repository including the implementation of the methods and FAIR data sets developed for the uncertainty evaluation of virtual experiments and digital twins, 2026).

1.8.2 Introduction to the uncertainty evaluation

There are multiple uncertainty sources that need to be considered to estimate the uncertainty of the results given by the DT. For this uncertainty estimation, the Monte Carlo Method is used.

The Monte Carlo method is a statistical and computational technique that performs a repeated random analysis to obtain an estimation of the uncertainty. Generally, the higher the number of iterations, the more accurate the estimation becomes.

Figure 28. Statistical analysis.

The most representative sources of uncertainty have been considered in the software, and are the ones shown in Table 7:

Uncertainty variable	Recommended probability distribution
Thermal resistivity of the soil	Uniform
Relative permittivity of the main insulation	Uniform
Electrical resistivity of the conductors	Uniform
Ambient temperature	Uniform
Cable laying (cable to cable distance)	Uniform

Cable dimensions (dimensions of each of the layers)	Uniform
Voltage	Normal
Length of each minor section	Uniform

Table 7. Probability distribution.

Both the types of distributions and their nominal values can be set up through the SPACS interface, shown in Figure 29:

Figure 29. Statistical distribution menu (with default values)

1.8.3 Interface for the uncertainty evaluation in static mode

To perform the Monte Carlo statistical analysis in SPACS, the user needs to follow a series of steps. Firstly, once the power line has been modelled, the “Análisis” (analysis) option must be selected in the toolbar, as shown in Figure 30. Subsequently, by clicking the “Análisis Estadístico” (statistical analysis) and “Variación de Parámetros Estático” (static parameter variation) options, the Monte Carlo analysis is initiated.

Figure 30. Monte Carlo analysis initialization

After following these steps, the menu previously shown in Figure 29, “Distribución

estadística de parámetros” (statistical distribution of the parameters), is displayed. In this menu, the user must specify the types of distributions and their nominal values.

1.8.4 Results of the uncertainty evaluation in static mode

Once the statistical analysis has been launched, SPACS calculates the results according to the specified distribution types. The output data is stored in two *.mat files, that are saved in a folder named “NAME/FILE/ORIGINAL_Estadístico”. This folder contains a subfolder labelled with the date and time of the analysis execution, as shown in Figure 31 (example of a real analysis).

Figure 31. Folders generated after launching the analysis.

Finally, to plot the contents of the folder, it is recommended to open the MATLAB Live Script [MC_result_analysis.mlx]. SPACS automatically generates the normal input and output distributions (stored in the folder in *.fig format). Nevertheless, for clearer interpretation of the results, the mentioned MATLAB script has been developed. Before running the Live Script, it is necessary to copy the folder created by SPACS into the “Resultados” folder. The “Resultados” folder should be located in the same directory as the Live Script, at the same hierarchical level. If it were not located on said folder, the path to the folder must be specified, as stated on the Live Script.

1.8.5 Use case

Finally, the uncertainty determination method of Monte Carlo included in the DT is tested with the model of the 220 kV power line previously described.

It must be considered that the section “Nivel de carga” (load level) of the “Distribución estadística de parámetros” (statistical distribution) menu is referred to the rated current of the cable. (The power line might be limited to lower currents than the ones allowed by the cable). This means that the percentage specified in the section must be calculated with respect to the aforementioned current ($I_{max} = 1457 A$ in this case study).

If the line’s rated current does not correspond to the cable’s maximum current, due to the limitation of another element, this must be considered when entering the data in the DT.

For example, in the case study, the rated power is 470 MVA, which is lower than the power that the cable could transmit if the maximum current were circulating through it. The 100% load that the power line actually allows corresponds to the following current:

$$S = \sqrt{3} \cdot U_L \cdot I_F \Rightarrow I_{F \text{ máx}} = \frac{S}{\sqrt{3} \cdot U} = \frac{470 \cdot 10^6}{\sqrt{3} \cdot 220 \cdot 10^3} \approx 1233 A \equiv 1,233 kA$$

Considering that the software associates the 100% load level with the cable’s maximum current I_{max} , the load level that must be entered into the software to simulate the 100% power line level is:

$$load_level(\%) = 100 \cdot \frac{1233}{1457} = 84.6\% \approx 85\%$$

The nominal values of the input variables that must be introduced in the “Distribución estadística de parámetros” (statistical distribution of the parameters) menu are the ones shown in Table 8 (for this specific example, only six of the eight uncertainty sources programmed in the DT are considered). All the considered uncertainty sources for this example have been modelled with uniform distributions.

Input variable	Reference value for the variation of the input variable
Thermal resistivity of the soil	$\pm 0.4 \text{ K} \cdot \text{m/W}$
Ambient temperature	$\pm 6 \text{ K}$
Cable to cable distance	$\pm 5 \%$
Cable diameter variation (of each layer)	$\pm 5 \%$
Electrical resistivity	$\pm 5\%$
Relative permittivity	$\pm 10\%$

Table 8. Reference value for the variation of the input variable

Both the reference values and the load level previously calculated are entered into SPACS. To obtain reliable results, it is recommended to run an analysis with 10,000 iterations. In Figure 32 the statistical distribution window with the necessary data already entered is shown.

Figure 32. Example of introduced data in the Statistical Distribution menu.

After launching the Monte Carlo analysis in the DT, the results are processed using the MATLAB Live Script [MC_results_analysis.mlx]. As previously described, this script displays a summary of the normal distributions obtained. The MATLAB script also provides the output mean values and their associated standard deviations. Once the standard deviation is known, assuming a 95% confidence interval, the expanded uncertainty associated with each variable is calculated ($U = k \cdot \sigma$). The uncertainty can also be expressed in relative terms based on the mean value obtained. These results are shown in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden..**

Variable	220kV - 470 MVA - example power line (case study)							
	Output distribution	Uncertainty estimation (k=2)						
Active conductor current		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>U_{F0}</td> <td>3.94 A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>U_{F4}</td> <td>2.85 A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>U_{F8}</td> <td>3.28 A</td> </tr> </table>	U_{F0}	3.94 A	U_{F4}	2.85 A	U_{F8}	3.28 A
	U_{F0}	3.94 A						
U_{F4}	2.85 A							
U_{F8}	3.28 A							
Sheath current CE3-SubA		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>U_{F0}</td> <td>1,39 A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>U_{F4}</td> <td>1,29 A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>U_{F8}</td> <td>1,34 A</td> </tr> </table>	U_{F0}	1,39 A	U_{F4}	1,29 A	U_{F8}	1,34 A
	U_{F0}	1,39 A						
U_{F4}	1,29 A							
U_{F8}	1,34 A							
Sheath current CE6-CE3		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>U_{F0}</td> <td>2,48 A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>U_{F4}</td> <td>2,50 A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>U_{F8}</td> <td>1,43 A</td> </tr> </table>	U_{F0}	2,48 A	U_{F4}	2,50 A	U_{F8}	1,43 A
	U_{F0}	2,48 A						
U_{F4}	2,50 A							
U_{F8}	1,43 A							

NOTE: With small mean values, the relative uncertainty may be high. Therefore, in such cases, it is advisable to consider the uncertainty in absolute terms.

Table 9. Results obtained with the Monte Carlo analysis and uncertainty estimation of the results of the DT for the use case studied.

Continuation of Table 9

<p>Sheath current CE9-CE6</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Sheath Current section CE9-CE6</p>	<table border="1" style="margin-bottom: 10px;"> <tr> <td>U_{F0}</td> <td>4,34 A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>U_{F4}</td> <td>4,07 A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>U_{F8}</td> <td>3,73 A</td> </tr> </table>	U_{F0}	4,34 A	U_{F4}	4,07 A	U_{F8}	3,73 A
U_{F0}	4,34 A							
U_{F4}	4,07 A							
U_{F8}	3,73 A							
<p>Sheath current CE12-CE9</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Sheath Current section CE12-CE9</p>	<table border="1" style="margin-bottom: 10px;"> <tr> <td>U_{F0}</td> <td>2,12 A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>U_{F4}</td> <td>3,25 A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>U_{F8}</td> <td>2,23 A</td> </tr> </table>	U_{F0}	2,12 A	U_{F4}	3,25 A	U_{F8}	2,23 A
U_{F0}	2,12 A							
U_{F4}	3,25 A							
U_{F8}	2,23 A							
<p>Sheath current SubB-CE12</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Sheath Current section SubB-CE12</p>	<table border="1" style="margin-bottom: 10px;"> <tr> <td>U_{F0}</td> <td>1,84 A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>U_{F4}</td> <td>1,81 A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>U_{F8}</td> <td>1,74 A</td> </tr> </table>	U_{F0}	1,84 A	U_{F4}	1,81 A	U_{F8}	1,74 A
U_{F0}	1,84 A							
U_{F4}	1,81 A							
U_{F8}	1,74 A							

1.8.6 Uncertainty evaluation in dynamic analysis

One of the key aspects of the DT SPACS is that it allows performing dynamic analysis of the behaviour of the cable system. That is, calculating the previously mentioned variables over time while considering the thermal transients caused by the changes of the load of the cable. The progressive heating or cooling of the cable (which causes transients of several hours) affects the results, therefore it must be considered. These calculations also introduce a certain uncertainty which must be

estimated.

For this uncertainty estimation, the Monte Carlo method is used again. As for the static analysis, the Monte Carlo method is executed within the SPACS graphical user interface. To do so, the user must select the “Análisis/Análisis estadístico/Variación de parámetros Dinámico” menu (Analysis/Statistical analysis/Dynamic parameter variation), as shown in Figure 33.

Figure 33. Selection of the dynamic parameter variation menu.

Following this step, the process is quite like the one followed for the static analysis. The “Dynamic parameter variation” window allows the user to configure the input distributions used to execute the Monte Carlo method. The interface is similar to the one shown in Figure 29, but with additional variables, related to the thermic calculations. Firstly, the heat diffusion coefficient of the terrain (α) is added. Secondly, apart from the ambient temperature that was specified in the static version, the temperature of the cable in the initial instant must be provided. The initial temperature is also given as a probability distribution, since it has an associated uncertainty.

The last distribution that must be specified is the one for the load level. This is due to the following reason. The load curve might represent three possibilities. First, it might be a theoretical curve, with no uncertainty associated, being only the input for the program, like the load level introduced on the static version. On the second place, it might be the sensor readings of an actual power line, and the user wants to study the behaviour of the power line by comparing the results of the software with the readings from the power line. In this case, the readings have uncertainty. Last, it might be a prediction of the load of the power line. These calculations are done regularly, but there is always uncertainty as the precise load level cannot be known beforehand.

After having introduced all the required data, the “OK” button is pressed, and a window opens, allowing the user to select a *.txt file containing the load current. It is given for one phase on a file in which the structure is as follows:

```

60
318.427841434620-
185.444006300445i
265.944624633356-
211.972233031187i
288.042530612421-
215.477678574478i
222.322355273649-
202.518439848398i
209.882103612360-
    
```

```
185.806703971914i  
211.208232453269-  
178.827533884735i
```

The first row represents the time interval between values (in minutes). In the following rows, each row represents the load current at a certain time, given as complex value. It is important to avoid blank spaces, as the software will not recognize them correctly. Note that this is a plain text file (txt), not a csv.

It is recommended to limit the number of registers entered (therefore, it is recommended to keep the sampling frequency low) so that the analysis will not take too much time. The software calculates all the variables for each register; therefore, the total execution time is proportional to the number of registers entered. Nevertheless, with high sampling frequencies, better results are obtained as the resolution of the output curves will be higher.

Figure 34. Dynamic parameter variation and selection of the load curve file.

Having introduced the load level of the power line, the analysis is performed. The output will be given in a similar way to the static analysis shown in the previous sections. But instead of consisting of discrete values, each variable is given as a set of curves for the whole timespan of the analysis (which corresponds to the one of the *.txt file introduced with the load values). Each curve represents one execution of the model. There will be as many curves as repetitions of the execution of the model have been requested to the software.

An example of the load curve and the currents through the sheaths obtained is shown in Figure 35. This is an example execution, with only 10 simulations, for the purpose of illustrating how the results are given.

Figure 35. Curves for a) the load current and b) sheath current for joint CE3.

2 Annex – Documentation for TWI benchmarking scenario and uncertainty evaluation methods

Simplified virtual experiment (benchmark scenario) and estimation methods

Table of Contents

Preliminary remarks.....	1
Introduction.....	1
The virtual experiment (VE) for the benchmark scenario.....	1
Execute : Setting environment & read input files.....	3
setting Environment.....	3
Measurements (virtual forward simulation).....	4
Execute : Setting uncertainties for parameters.....	4
Execute : Draw a specific realization for virtual experiment.....	5
Execute : Simulate forward experiment.....	6
Result on CCD.....	6
The measurement model / data analysis for the benchmark scenario.....	7
Obtaining estimates for the measurand.....	8
Execute : f1 and plot topography.....	8
Execute : Plot estimated parameter vs. ground truth.....	9
Residual	10
Saving Workspace.....	11
Git information.....	11

Preliminary remarks

The following development implements a **simplified**, i.e., linearized variant of the tilted-wave interferometer (TWI) and prepares uncertainty evaluation for this simplified model. Moreover, important concepts, such as model correction and post-processing of the form reconstruction result obtained (reconstruction of higher spatial frequencies and position and orientation correction of the surface under test) are not performed in this study. This means, the measurand of this simplified model differs from the measurand of the real TWI, and **the results obtained here are not representative for the quality of the actual TWI** and the obtained uncertainties may differ significantly to those obtained in the real experiment. It is to note that here and in the following, when referring to the TWI, the simplified and linearized version is considered.

Introduction

In this notebook, a benchmark scenario is developed that applies the concepts of the simplified TWI in a simple and numerically efficient way to define a virtual experiment. For that, a linearization of the TWI is considered that has been generated from analytical and numerical derivatives of the actual TWI simulation model. The combination of this linear simulation (or forward) model with a simple additive Gaussian noise assumption, provides the virtual experiment under consideration for this task.

This document introduces only the employed VE and provides an estimation strategy for the underlying measurand. Other documents will use these concepts for uncertainty evaluation.

The virtual experiment (VE) for the benchmark scenario

The considered virtual experiment is of the following form

$$x^{ve} = G(y, z, e) \approx A[y, z] + e = A_y y + A_z z + e, \quad e \text{ realization of } E \sim N(0, \sigma^2 I).$$

Here, the matrix A has the size of $n \times p$, with $n \gg p$ and it is the result of the linearization from the complex TWI chosen for a specific realistic scenario, without further details. The actual VE is hence approximated by the corresponding linear function and Gaussian measurement noise model. The sub-matrices A_y and A_z correspond to different parameter influences. y represent values for Y , which denotes the measurand. Similarly, z represent realizations of Z , which is a multivariate parameter with Type-B information that is unknown. The statistical fluctuation of repeated measurements are represented by e , which is assumed to follow a Gaussian noise model with known standard deviation $\sigma > 0$. In particular, we consider

Symbol of value	Symbol of Quantity	Quantity description	Distribution	Comment
x^{ve}	X^{ve}	Deviations of optical path differences from a nominal system	Multivariate type A quantity	Abbreviated: OPDDs (optical path difference differences)
y	Y	Parametric description of measurand and position of Surface Under Test (SUT) in x and y direction.	-	Coefficients of Zernike polynomials, Position of SUT in x and y direction
z	Z	Collection of different elements of the VE, each consists of 6 parameters (3 position parameter in m and 3 rotation/orientation parameter in rad): - Zoom Optics - Collimator - Image Optics - Beamsplitter - CCDP_RMS_LIN1 - Source Plane - Surface Under Test (SUT), but only those which are not in y. Additionally, the wavelength in m is considered.	multivariate Gaussian	Quantities with Type B information
e	E	Measurement noise	multivariate Gaussian	Standard deviation is assumed to be known as $\sigma = 10^{-8}$ m

Note that we write the quantities with upper case letters and specific values for these quantities with lower case letters.

Execute : Setting environment & read input files

The matrices A_Y and A_Z for a specific measurement scenario are provided in the DATA directory and can be loaded using the following commands.

setting Environment

```
clear all;
addpath ('HELPERS');
fprintf ('\n=====
\n Execution at
"%s"
\n=====
\n', string(datetime));
```

```
=====
Execution at "29-Oct-2025 18:28:48"
=====
```

```
PATH_DATA = fullfile ('.', 'DATA', 'C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom');
fprintf ('Environment:
\nPATH_DATA = %s
\n\n', PATH_DATA);
```

```
Environment:
PATH_DATA = ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom
```

```
% Reading Sensitivity Files
J = t_jacs (PATH_DATA, true);
J.load_all;
```

```
reading all parameters:
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/pccd.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/img_key.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/rcn.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_rcn.mat ...done (4.40559s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/par_rcn.mat ...done (0.280914s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/bsp.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_bsp.mat ...done (0.364745s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/ccd.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_ccd.mat ...done (0.39181s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/col.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_col.mat ...done (0.405774s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/img.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_img.mat ...done (0.344626s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/src.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_src.mat ...done (0.329864s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/sut.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_sut.mat ...done (0.306551s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/wvl.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_wvl.mat ...done (0.123742s).
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/zom.mat ...
reading file ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/mask_zom.mat ...done (0.338652s).
```

```
J_SUT = J.get_obj ("sut");
J_SUT.mask_y = [true true false, false, false, false];
J_SUT.mask_z = ~J_SUT.mask_y;

A_Y = J.get_jac ('y'); % Operator corresponding to Zernike coefficients
& xy parameter
A_Z = J.get_jac ('z'); % other parameter
```

Measurements (virtual forward simulation)

We consider that a set of measurements from the experiment are given

$$x = (x_1, \dots, x_m),$$

which are realizations of the measured quantity X . For illustration purposes, we consider measurements which are realizations of the VE, that includes all uncertainty contributions, i.e. that corresponds to the X^{vc} that is the output of the VE, i.e., optical path length difference differences (OPDDs). For more details about the actual quantities involved, cf. [Fortmeier2022].

Each quantity as defined in the table above, is assigned an uncertainty. In the following different uncertainties are considered, cf. the cases below in the code:

Execute : Setting uncertainties for parameters

```
J_rcn = J.get_obj ('rcn'); %
sensitivity for zernike coefficients (sut = surface under test)

case_nr = '0001';
switch case_nr
  case '0001'

    sigma = 10e-9; % noise of about 10 nm
    std_ucy = 0;
    factor_sut = 1;
    factor_wvl = 0;
    vec_sut = factor_sut*[5e-5 5e-5 0e-6, 3e-4 3e-4, 3e-4];
    par_y = J_rcn.ground_truth_T_DIFF_alpha_nm (J_rcn.mask_y,3); % No
    uncertainty is assigned to the Zernike coefficients,... %

  since it is the measurand (not true for Bayesian approach)
  case '0002'
    sigma = 10e-9;
    std_ucy = 0;
    factor_sut = 0;
    factor_wvl = 0;
    vec_sut = factor_sut*[0 0 0 0 0 0];
    par_y = J_rcn.ground_truth_T_DIFF_alpha_nm (J_rcn.mask_y,3);
  case '0003'
    sigma = 10e-9;
    std_ucy = 0;
    factor_sut = 0;
    factor_wvl = 0;
    vec_sut = factor_sut*[0 0 0 0 0 0];
    par_y = 0;
  case '0004'
    sigma = 10e-9;
    std_ucy = 0;
    factor_sut = 1;
```

```

    factor_wvl = 0;
    vec_sut    = factor_sut*[5e-6 5e-6 1e-6, 3e-4 3e-4, 3e-4];
    par_y      = J_rcn.ground_truth_T_DIFF_alpha_nm (J_rcn.mask_y,3);
case 'all'
    sigma = 10e-9;
    std_ucy    = [3e-6 3e-6 3e-6 3e-4 3e-4 3e-4];
    factor_sut = 1;
    factor_wvl = 1;
    vec_sut    = factor_sut*[5e-6 5e-6 1e-6, 3e-4 3e-4, 3e-4];
    par_y      = J_rcn.ground_truth_T_DIFF_alpha_nm (J_rcn.mask_y,3);
otherwise
    error ('unknown case_nr %s', case_nr);
end

J_rcn = J.get_obj ('rcn');
sensitivity for Zernike coefficients (sut = surface under test)
J.get_obj("rcn").par_y = par_y;
uncertainty is assigned to the Zernike coefficients, ...

J.get_obj("bsp").U = std_ucy;
beamsplitter
J.get_obj("ccd").U = std_ucy;
very small uncertainty
J.get_obj("col").U = std_ucy;
collimator just very small uncertainty
J.get_obj("img").U = std_ucy;
plane just very small uncertainty
J.get_obj("src").U = std_ucy;
plane just very small uncertainty
J_SUT.U = vec_sut;
J.get_obj("wvl").U = factor_wvl*2.8e-12;
wavelength uncertainty according to A1.2.1 report
J.get_obj("zom").U = std_ucy;
objectives, just very small uncertainty

```

According to the uncertainties assigned above, a random realization is drawn in the following for the quantities Y and Z of the virtual experiment.

Execute : Draw a specific realization for virtual experiment

```

J.set_par_U_rand;
generates a realization according to uncertainties defined in object
J.disp_par ('y', case_nr);

=====
case 0001 (y)
=====

rcn : [NaN          NaN          NaN  -4.22524e-09  4.333582e-07  2.661929e-08  1.009117e-08 ...]
bsp : [NaNm NaNm NaNm NaNrad NaNrad NaNrad]
ccd : [NaNm NaNm NaNm NaNrad NaNrad NaNrad]

```

```
col : [NaN NaNm NaNm NaNrad NaNrad NaNrad]
img : [NaNm NaNm NaNm NaNrad NaNrad NaNrad]
src : [NaNm NaNm NaNm NaNrad NaNrad NaNrad]
sut : [2.21312e-05m 3.02715e-05m NaNm NaNrad NaNrad NaNrad]
wvl : NaN pm
zom : [NaNm NaNm NaNm NaNrad NaNrad NaNrad]
```

```
J.disp_par ('z', case_nr);
```

```
=====
case 0001 (z)
=====
```

```
rcn : [NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN ...]
bsp : [-0m -0m 0m -0rad -0rad 0rad]
ccd : [0m 0m 0m 0rad -0rad 0rad]
col : [-0m 0m -0m -0rad 0rad 0rad]
img : [-0m -0m 0m 0rad 0rad 0rad]
src : [-0m -0m -0m 0rad -0rad -0rad]
sut : [NaNm NaNm -0m 0.000260454rad 0.000405199rad -8.68403e-05rad]
wvl : -0 pm
zom : [-0m 0m -0m 0rad 0rad 0rad]
```

Execute : Simulate forward experiment

```
y_ground_truth = zeros (size (A_Y,2),1); % ground truth, no position errors,
sut = design surface (no difference zenike)
ix_xy = (size(y_ground_truth,1)-sum(J_SUT.mask_y)+1):size(y_ground_truth,1);
ix_ai = 1:(size(y_ground_truth,1)-sum(J_SUT.mask_y));
ai_key = find (J.get_obj("rcn").mask_y);
xy_key = find (J_SUT.mask_y);
n_xy = length(ix_xy);
n_ai = length(ix_ai);

y_ground_truth(ix_xy) = J_SUT.par_y (J_SUT.mask_y);
y_ground_truth(ix_ai) = J_rcn.par_y (J_rcn.mask_y); % some ground truth
that we want to reconstruct later

yzw_realization = J.get_par('a'); % returns current random realization

A = J.get_jac('a'); % returns full matrix A. Columns
correspond to sub-matrices above

OPDD = A * yzw_realization;
OPDD = OPDD + sigma * randn(size(OPDD));
```

Result OPDD on CCD

```
plot_ccd_fwd(J, OPDD); % Plot the data (comma prevents
second output of image in notebook)
```


Example OPDDs that are generated by the benchmark TWI. The root-mean-square value over the 2D plane is given over each image. The four images correspond to a single measurement, since different illumination settings of the specimen are considered. These generated observations are dominated by position effects and would be corrected in a real measurement scenario prior to the reconstruction of the topography (measurement).

The measurement model / data analysis for the benchmark scenario

The choice of the measurement model is generally ambiguous when using a virtual experiment as above. This is, since many measurement models can be derived that correspond to the virtual experiment above, e.g. the choice of estimation parameters is often not uniquely defined.

A common choice for a measurement model that involves the interpretation as a regression model can, due to the linearity of the VE, be written as the solution of a corresponding linear least-squares problem. Since a measurement model is given in terms of quantities and not values, we use here the corresponding upper case letters

$$Y_1 = f_1(X, Z) = \operatorname{argmin}_{\tilde{Y}} \|X - (A_y \tilde{Y} + A_z Z)\|_2^2.$$

This means, for a specific realization of x and z , the corresponding estimate for Y_1 is given by

$$\hat{Y}_1 = A_y^\dagger (x - A_z z),$$

where A_y^\dagger denotes the pseudo-inverse matrix of A_y .

It is to mention that the measurement model f_1 is partially inverse to the deterministic part of the VE, i.e. the forward model, if and only if the matrix A_y has full rank. In particular, for some y and z it holds

$$f_1(G(y, z, 0), z) = f_1(A_y y + A_z z, z) = A_y^+(A_y y + A_z z - A_z z) = (A_y^+ A_y) y.$$

Obtaining estimates for the measurand

For the measurement model that we consider, the estimate can be obtained by simply applying f_1 .

Execute : f1 and plot topography

```
% inverse Matrix
A_Y_p = pinv (A_Y);
% define f1
f1 = @(x_, z_) A_Y_p*(x_ - A_Z*z_);
% execute f1
z_zeros = zeros (size(A_Z,2),1);
hat_y_1 = f1(OPDD, z_zeros);

figla = figure;
figla.Position = [0 0 2560 1080];
h1 = subplot (1,3,1,'parent', figla);
ai_est = hat_y_1(ix_ai);
plot_topo_ai (h1, J_rcn, ai_est, 'est. diff. topo (z=0)');
h2 = subplot (1,3,2,'parent', figla);
ai_gt = y_ground_truth(ix_ai);
plot_topo_ai (h2, J_rcn, ai_gt, 'ground truth diff. topo');
h3 = subplot (1,3,3,'parent', figla);
ai_res = ai_est-ai_gt;
plot_topo_ai (h3, J_rcn, ai_res, 'residual');
```


In the figure above, we show the estimated measurand, i.e. the estimated difference topography and the ground truth difference topography used to generate the measurements. The remaining residual arises due to the fact that for estimating the difference topography we have chosen $z=0$, which is different to the ground truth (depending on the case).

Execute : Plot estimated parameter vs. ground truth

```
function plot_parameter (a_h, a_ix, a_par, a_par_gt, a_legendcellstr,
a_title)
    scatter (a_h{1}, round(a_ix), a_par, 'bx'); hold (a_h{1}, 'on');
    scatter (a_h{1}, round(a_ix), a_par_gt, 'ro'); hold (a_h{1}, 'off');
    legend (a_h{1}, a_legendcellstr);
    xlabel (a_h{1}, 'index');
    ylabel (a_h{1}, 'parameter value / m');
    title (a_h{1}, a_title);
    xlim (a_h{1}, [0, max(a_ix)+1]);

    scatter (a_h{2}, round(a_ix), a_par-a_par_gt, 'gx');
    xlabel (a_h{2}, 'index');
    ylabel (a_h{2}, ' residual / m');
    title (a_h{2}, sprintf ('residual (%s)', a_title));
    xlim (a_h{2}, [0, max(a_ix)+1]);

end

fig1 = figure;
fig1.Position = [0 0 1920 1080];
h12{1} = subplot (2,2,1,'parent', fig1);
h22{1} = subplot (2,2,2,'parent', fig1);
h12{2} = subplot (2,2,3,'parent', fig1);
h22{2} = subplot (2,2,4,'parent', fig1);
plot_parameter (h12, xy_key, hat_y_1(ix_xy), y_ground_truth(ix_xy), {'xy
parameter', 'ground truth'}, 'Sut pos.')
plot_parameter (h22, ai_key, hat_y_1(ix_ai), y_ground_truth(ix_ai),
{'estimated zernike', 'ground truth'}, 'Zernike coefficient')
plot_parameter (h22, ai_key, hat_y_1(ix_ai), y_ground_truth(ix_ai),
{'estimated zernike', 'ground truth'}, 'Zernike coefficient')
```

```
plot_parameter (h22, ai_key, hat_y_1(ix_ai), y_ground_truth(ix_ai),
{'estimated zernike', 'ground truth'}, 'Zernike coefficient')
```


Residual

```

rsd = OPDD - A_Y*hat_y_1;

A_opl_sut = J_SUT.jac_opl;
n_rays = size(A_opl_sut(:,3),1);
R = sparse(1:n_rays, 1:n_rays, A_opl_sut(:,3)); % diagonal matrix
dZ = R*rsd;

plot_ccd_fwd(J, rsd);
    
```


The image above shows the resulting residuals when comparing the measurement OPDDs and the generated OPDDs using the estimated parameter \hat{y} . It can be seen that the deviations compare to the assumed standard deviation of the Gaussian noise $\sigma = 10$ nm.

Saving Workspace

```
% saving Workspace
fn_name_vexp = fullfile (PATH_DATA, "workspace_virtexp.mat");
save_workspace_mlx(fn_name_vexp);
```

saving workspace (fwd): ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/workspace_virtexp.mat ...done (110.893s).

Git information

```
mygit = gitrepo;
disp (mygit.CurrentBranch);
```

GitBranch with properties:

```
    Name: "main"
  LastCommit: [1x1 GitCommit] (c6a1cbe)
```

```
disp (mygit.CurrentBranch.LastCommit);
```

GitCommit with properties:

Message: "RC -Candidate for Report."
ID: "c6alcbcd7cee699bd09de2da803fc0bfcbc68239"
AuthorName: "Manuel Stavridis"
AuthorEmail: "Manuel.Stavridis@ptb.de"
AuthorDate: 28-Oct-2025 19:47:06 +0000
CommitterName: "Manuel Stavridis"
CommitterEmail: "Manuel.Stavridis@ptb.de"
CommitterDate: 28-Oct-2025 19:47:06 +0000
ParentCommits: "916c492d5f0e88ea644d81508b2214f49ca84205"

```
disp (mygit.ModifiedFiles);
```

```
"/home/stavri01/SharedData/MU/VIDIT/WP1/Benchmark/TWI/HELPERS/run_export_result.mlx"  
"/home/stavri01/SharedData/MU/VIDIT/WP1/Benchmark/TWI/run_fwd_ve.mlx"  
"/home/stavri01/SharedData/MU/VIDIT/WP1/Benchmark/TWI/run_ncy_mcve.mlx"  
"/home/stavri01/SharedData/MU/VIDIT/WP1/Benchmark/TWI/run_ncy_sota.mlx"
```

Uncertainty evaluation methods according state of the art (sota)

Table of Contents

Preliminary remarks.....	1
Introduction.....	1
The virtual experiment (VE) for the benchmark scenario.....	2
Commonly used methods for uncertainty evaluation.....	2
Law of propagation of uncertainties (LPU) using data analysis (DA).....	2
Execute : LPU using DA	3
Law of propagation of uncertainties (LPU) using the virtual experiment (VE).....	6
Propagation of distribution (PoD) applied to the data analysis (DA).....	7
Execute : PoD applied to DA.....	7
Propagation of distribution (PoD) applied to the virtual experiment (VE) followed by the data analysis (DA).....	12
Execute: POD applied to VE followed by DA.....	12
Result collection	17
Using measurement model f1	17
Position parameter (xy) estimate.....	17
Position parameter (xy) standard deviation.....	17
Zernike parameter (ai) estimate.....	18
Zernike parameter (ai) standard deviation.....	18
Using measurement model f2	19
Position parameter (xy) estimate.....	19
Position parameter (xy) standard deviation.....	19
Zernike parameter (ai) estimate.....	20
Zernike parameter (ai) standard deviation.....	20
Conclusion.....	21
Git information.....	21

Preliminary remarks

The following development implements a **simplified**, i.e., linearized variant of the tilted-wave interferometer (TWI) and provides uncertainty evaluation for this simplified model. Moreover, important concepts, such as model correction and post-processing of the form reconstruction result obtained (reconstruction of higher spatial frequencies and position and orientation correction of the surface under test) are not performed in this study. This means, the measurand of this simplified model differs from the measurand of the real TWI, and **the results obtained here are not representative for the quality of the actual TWI** and the obtained uncertainties may differ significantly to those obtained in the real experiment. It is to note that here and in the following, when referring to the TWI, the simplified and linearized version is considered.

Introduction

In this notebook, a benchmark scenario is developed that applies the concepts of the simplified TWI in a simple and numerically efficient way to define a virtual experiment. For that, a linearization of the TWI is considered that has been generated from analytical and numerical derivatives of the actual TWI simulation model. The combination of this linear simulation (or forward) model with a simple additive Gaussian noise assumption, provides the virtual experiment under consideration for this task.

Subsequently, several uncertainty estimation methods are implemented and applied for this specific virtual experiment and two different measurement models. Several cases are distinguished that consider different uncertainties of the input parameters.

The virtual experiment (VE) for the benchmark scenario

please refer to *run_fwd.mlx*

```
%% setting Environment
clear all;
addpath ('HELPERS');

N_mc = 1e6; % Number of Monte Carlo Runs
fprintf ('\n===== \n Execution
at "%s" (N_mc=%d)\n===== \n',
string(datetime), N_mc);
```

```
=====
Execution at "29-Oct-2025 19:05:10" (N_mc=1000000)
=====
```

```
PATH_DATA = fullfile ('.', 'DATA', 'C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom');

fn_name_vexp = fullfile (PATH_DATA, "workspace_virtexp.mat");
h_time_load = tic;
fprintf ('loading forward experiment: "%s"', fn_name_vexp);
```

```
loading forward experiment: "./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/workspace_virtexp.mat"
```

```
load (fn_name_vexp);
fprintf ('done (%gs)', toc(h_time_load));
```

```
done (26.6977s)
```

Commonly used methods for uncertainty evaluation

Law of propagation of uncertainties (LPU) using data analysis (DA)

This uncertainty evaluation method does not use the VE explicitly, but it may have been used to identify and validate the input quantities and their uncertainty.

The method computes the covariance of the measurand using the law of propagation of uncertainties. For this, the input covariance needs to be defined. In our case, we set

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} U_X & 0 \\ 0 & U_Z \end{bmatrix}.$$

Then, the covariance of the measurand is given by

$$U_Y = J_f U_f J_f^T$$

where J_f is the derivative of the corresponding measurement model with respect to the measurand and U_f denotes the sub-matrix of U that contains all uncertainties considered in the current measurement model.

For this demonstration, we employ two different measurement models. On the one hand, we take the same model function as in the previous document on the definition of the forward experiment

$$Y_1 = f_1(X, Z) = A_Y^+(X - A_Z Z).$$

where A_Y^+ is the pseudo-inverse of the matrix A_Y used in the forward model

$$x^{ve} = A_Y y + A_Z z + \epsilon.$$

For details, cf. the previous live script corresponding to the forward model and the virtual experiment.

On the other hand, we define a simplified measurement model that (naively) ignores the contribution in the additional parameters Z by fixing the value for $z = 0$. In this case the measurement model is given by

$$Y_2 = f_2(X, Z) = f_2(X) = A_Y^+(X).$$

By denoting the pseudo-inverse of A_Y by $A_Y^+ = (A_Y^T A_Y)^{-1} A_Y^T$, it follows that

- $J_{f_1} = [A_Y^+ \quad -A_Y^+ A_Z]$ and $U_f = \text{diag}(U_X, U_Z)$
- $J_{f_2} = [A_Y^+]$ and $U_f = U_X$

Execute : LPU using DA

```
function plot_unc_errorbar (a_h, a_ix, a_est, a_std, a_groundtruth,
a_title)
    errorbar(a_h, a_ix, a_est, a_std, "-
s", "MarkerSize", 5, "MarkerEdgeColor", "blue", "MarkerFaceColor", [0.65 0.85
0.90], 'Linestyle', 'none');
    hold (a_h, 'on');
    scatter (a_h, a_ix, a_groundtruth, 'ro');
    hold (a_h, 'off');
    set (a_h, 'FontSize', 11);
    xlim (a_h, [0, max(a_ix)+1]);
    legend (a_h, {'estimated coefficients', 'ground truth'});
    xlabel (a_h, 'index');
    ylabel (a_h, 'parameter value / m');
    title (a_h, a_title);
end

% Definition of f2. Commonly used methods for uncertainty evaluation
% f1 and hat_y_1 is already defined and saved in run_fwd_ve.
f2 = @(x_) A_Y_p*(x_); %
% execute f2
hat_y_2 = f2(OPDD);

U_X = sigma^2 * speye (size (OPDD,1));
```

```

U_Z = diag (J.get_U).^2;

U_Y_1 = A_Y_p*U_X*A_Y_p' + A_Y_p*A_Z*U_Z*A_Z' *A_Y_p';
U_Y_2 = A_Y_p*U_X*A_Y_p';

fig2 = figure;
fig2.Position = [0, 0, 1980, 1024];

h1 = subplot (1,4,1,'parent', fig2);
plot_unc_errorbar (h1, xy_key, hat_y_1(ix_xy),
2*sqrt(diag(U_Y_1(ix_xy,ix_xy))), y_ground_truth(ix_xy), 'SUT pos. (f1)');

h2 = subplot (1,4,2,'parent', fig2);
plot_unc_errorbar (h2, xy_key, hat_y_2(ix_xy),
2*sqrt(diag(U_Y_2(ix_xy,ix_xy))), y_ground_truth(ix_xy), 'SUT pos. (f2)');

h3 = subplot (1,4,3,'parent', fig2);
plot_unc_errorbar (h3, ai_key, hat_y_1(ix_ai),
2*sqrt(diag(U_Y_1(ix_ai,ix_ai))), y_ground_truth(ix_ai), 'zernike (f1)');

h4 = subplot (1,4,4,'parent', fig2);
plot_unc_errorbar (h4, ai_key, hat_y_2(ix_ai),
2*sqrt(diag(U_Y_2(ix_ai,ix_ai))), y_ground_truth(ix_ai), 'zernike (f2)');

```


In this figure the resulting estimates and uncertainties from the two measurement models are compared to the ground-truth values considered for this example. It can directly be seen that the uncertainties resulting from the

measurement model f_2 are much smaller than from using f_1 , which is clear due to the missing influence of the Z parameter

```
fig21 = figure;
fig21.Position = [0, 0, 1980, 1024];
h1 = subplot (1,2,1, 'Parent', fig21);
h2 = subplot (1,2,2, 'Parent', fig21);
p_ncy = get_ncy_sut(J_rcn, U_Y_1(ix_ai,ix_ai), []);
plot_topo_xyz (h1, p_ncy, 'Uncertainty LPU->DA, (f1)');
p_ncy = get_ncy_sut(J_rcn, U_Y_2(ix_ai,ix_ai), []);
plot_topo_xyz (h2, p_ncy, 'Uncertainty LPU->DA, (f2)');
```


Pixel-wise uncertainty resulting from the uncertainty evaluation method above. On the left, measurement model f_1 is used and on the right result for f_2 is presented.

```
TABLE_LPU_xy = table (hat_y_1(ix_xy), hat_y_2(ix_xy), sqrt(diag(U_Y_1(ix_xy,
ix_xy))), sqrt(diag(U_Y_2(ix_xy, ix_xy))));
TABLE_LPU_xy.Properties.VariableNames = {'f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m', 'f2
est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m', 'f1 std. (Sut pos. x,y) / m', 'f2 std. (Sut pos.
x,y) / m'};
TABLE_LPU_xy
```

TABLE_LPU_xy = 2×4 table

	f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m	f2 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m
1	4.2187e-05	4.2187e-05

	f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m	f2 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m
2	1.7883e-05	1.7883e-05

```
TABLE_LPU_ai = table (hat_y_1(ix_ai), hat_y_2(ix_ai),
sqrt(diag(U_Y_1(ix_ai,ix_ai))), sqrt(diag(U_Y_2(ix_ai,ix_ai))));
TABLE_LPU_ai.Properties.VariableNames = {'f1 est. (ai) / m', 'f2 est. (ai) /
m', 'f1 std. (ai) / m', 'f2 std. (ai) / m'};
TABLE_LPU_ai
```

TABLE_LPU_ai = 228x4 table

	f1 est. (ai) / m	f2 est. (ai) / m	f1 std. (ai) / m	f2 std. (ai) / m
1	3.5003e-08	3.5003e-08	1.3560e-07	3.7592e-11
2	4.3334e-07	4.3334e-07	2.3754e-11	2.3484e-11
3	2.6586e-08	2.6586e-08	4.2649e-11	4.1472e-11
4	2.8545e-08	2.8545e-08	2.1290e-08	3.9662e-11
5	-2.5077e-09	-2.5077e-09	7.5348e-09	3.4602e-11
6	4.6955e-09	4.6955e-09	2.6225e-10	2.7652e-11
7	-9.4916e-09	-9.4916e-09	7.7970e-11	3.5831e-11
8	-2.8372e-10	-2.8372e-10	8.3029e-09	3.1874e-11
9	-8.6884e-09	-8.6884e-09	1.1394e-08	2.9945e-11
10	4.8656e-08	4.8656e-08	3.0867e-11	2.4838e-11
11	-4.8269e-08	-4.8269e-08	4.6366e-11	3.6844e-11
12	5.1888e-09	5.1888e-09	4.5998e-11	4.3141e-11
13	-1.2990e-09	-1.2990e-09	1.9152e-09	3.7463e-11
14	-3.3544e-09	-3.3544e-09	1.6664e-09	3.5087e-11

⋮

It can be seen, that the measurement model f_2 , which ignores the uncertainty in the parameters generates a much smaller uncertainty in the considered coefficients, which also does not cover the true value of some of the parameters.

On the other hand, using the uncertainty of the parameters, the uncertainty of the considered coefficients is much larger, but covers the ground truth values.

Law of propagation of uncertainties (LPU) using the virtual experiment (VE)

In these approaches, only the VE is considered instead of the measurement model. For the *linear weighted least-squares* approach, the variability in the parameters is ignored and the resulting covariance reads as follows

$$U_{Y_1} = (J_Y^T U_X^{-1} J_Y)^{-1} = (A_Y^T U_X^{-1} A_Y)^{-1}$$

where J_Y denotes the Jacobian of the VE with respect to the measurand and the second equality follows due to our considered VE in (1), i.e., it holds $J_Y = A_Y$. Then, the following formula for the covariance of the measurand follows from matrix algebra and the properties of the pseudo-inverse in this case

$$\begin{aligned} U_{Y_1} &= (A_Y^T U_X^{-1} A_Y)^{-1} = ((A_Y A_Y^+ A_Y)^T U_X^{-1} A_Y A_Y^+ A_Y)^{-1} = (A_Y (A_Y^T A_Y)^{-1} A_Y^T A_Y)^T U_X^{-1} A_Y (A_Y^T A_Y)^{-1} A_Y^T A_Y)^{-1} \\ &= (A_Y^T A_Y)^{-1} ((A_Y (A_Y^T A_Y)^{-1})^T U_X^{-1} A_Y (A_Y^T A_Y)^{-1})^{-1} (A_Y^T A_Y)^{-1} = A_Y^+ U_X (A_Y^+)^T \end{aligned}$$

which is equivalent to the result of the previous section using the measurement model f_2 .

At the same time, the approach following the implicit function theorem is based on the formulation of the implicit function

$$h(X, Y, Z) = Y - A_Y^+ X - A_Y^+ A_Z Z$$

and covariance of the measurand can be derived using the corresponding partial derivatives, i.e. $J_Y = I$ denoting the derivative of h with respect to the measurand and $J_{X,Z} = [-A_Y^+ \quad -A_Y^+ A_Z]$ denotes the matrix comprising the derivatives of h with respect to X and Z . Then it follows

$$U_{Y_2} = J_Y^{-1} J_{X,Z} U J_{X,Z}^T J_Y^{-T} = A_Y^+ U_X (A_Y^+)^T + A_Y^+ A_Z U_Z A_Z^T (A_Y^+)^T$$

which is again equivalent to the first approach of the previous section using the measurement model f_1 .

Propagation of distribution (PoD) applied to the data analysis (DA)

In this section, the propagation of distribution (PoD) approach using the measurement model is considered. This approach generates a probability density function for the measurand using the following algorithm

- For $i=1, \dots, N$
- $e_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2 I)$
- Draw a z_i according to assumed covariance U_i
- Generate disturbed data $\tilde{x} = X - A_Z z_i + e_i$
- Compute $y_i = f(\tilde{x}, z_i)$
- Summarize sample y_1, \dots, y_n

Execute : PoD applied to DA

```
y1_list_xy = zeros (N_mc, n_xy);
y2_list_xy = zeros (N_mc, n_xy);
y1_list_ai = zeros (N_mc, n_ai);
y2_list_ai = zeros (N_mc, n_ai);

n_worker = 50;
open_parallel_pool (n_worker);
parfor i=1:N_mc
    epsi = 0; % randn(size(dOPD))*sigma;
```

```

    J.set_par_U_rand; % generates a realization
    according to uncertainties defined in object
    zi = J.get_par('z'); % returns current random
    realization
    xi_da = OPDD - A_Z*zi + epsi;
    y1_list_i = f1(xi_da, zi);
    y2_list_i = f2(xi_da);
    y1_list_xy(i,:) = y1_list_i(ix_xy);
    y2_list_xy(i,:) = y2_list_i(ix_xy);

    y1_list_ai(i,:) = y1_list_i(ix_ai);
    y2_list_ai(i,:) = y2_list_i(ix_ai);

end

U_y1 = cov(y1_list_ai);
U_y2 = cov(y2_list_ai);

f1_est_ai = mean(y1_list_ai)';
f2_est_ai = mean(y2_list_ai)';
f1_std_ai = std(y1_list_ai)';
f2_std_ai = std(y2_list_ai)';

f1_est_xy = mean(y1_list_xy)';
f2_est_xy = mean(y2_list_xy)';
f1_std_xy = std(y1_list_xy)';
f2_std_xy = std(y2_list_xy)';

fig_31 = figure;
fig_31.Position = [0 0 1920 1024];

h1 = subplot (2,2,1, 'parent', fig_31);
p_ncy = get_ncy_sut(J_rcn, U_y1, []);
plot_topo_xyz (h1, p_ncy, sprintf('Uncertainty DA (f1, N=%d)', N_mc));
h2 = subplot (2,2,2, 'parent', fig_31);
p_ncy = get_ncy_sut(J_rcn, U_y2, []);
plot_topo_xyz (h2, p_ncy, sprintf('Uncertainty DA (f2, N=%d)', N_mc));
h3 = subplot (2,2,3, 'parent', fig_31);
plot_topo_ai (h3, J_rcn, f1_est_ai, sprintf('Estimate DA (f1, N=%d)', N_mc));
h4 = subplot (2,2,4, 'parent', fig_31 );
plot_topo_ai (h4, J_rcn, f2_est_ai, sprintf ('Estimate DA (f2, N=%d)',
N_mc));

```

Uncertainty DA (f1, N=1000000)

Uncertainty DA (f2, N=1000000)

Estimate DA (f1, N=1000000)

Estimate DA (f2, N=1000000)


```
function plot_histogram (a_h, a_unc_v, a_x_label, a_y_label, a_title)
    histogram (a_h, a_unc_v, 100, EdgeColor='none', Normalization = 'pdf');
    xlabel (a_h, a_x_label);
    ylabel (a_h, a_y_label);
    title (a_h, a_title);
end

fig_32 = figure;
fig_32.Position = [0 0 1920 1024];
xy_tiltes = {'SUT pos x', 'Sut pos y'};
for i=1:n_xy
    h1 = subplot (2,n_xy,i, 'parent', fig_32); % axis (h1, 'equal');
    h2 = subplot (2,n_xy,i+n_xy, 'parent', fig_32); % axis (h2, 'equal');
    if i==1
        tmp_title = 'x';
    elseif i == 2
        tmp_title = 'y';
    end

    plot_histogram (h1, y1_list_xy(:,i), sprintf('pos. deviation / m'),
        'Probability density (f1)', xy_tiltes{i});
    plot_histogram (h2, y2_list_xy(:,i), sprintf('pos. deviation / m'),
        'Probability density (f2)', xy_tiltes{i});
end
```



```

n_ai_5 = 5;
for i=1:n_ai_5
    h1 = subplot (2,n_ai_5,i, 'parent', fig_32); % axis (h1, 'equal');
    h2 = subplot (2,n_ai_5,i+n_ai_5, 'parent', fig_32); % axis (h2, 'equal');

    plot_histogram (h1, y1_list_ai(:,i), sprintf('zern. a_%d / m',
ai_key(i)), 'Probability density (f1)', sprintf('a_%d',ai_key(i)));
    plot_histogram (h2, y2_list_ai(:,i), sprintf('zern. a_%d / m',
ai_key(i)), 'Probability density (f2)', sprintf('a_%d',ai_key(i)));
end

```



```
TABLE_POD_xy = table (f1_est_xy, f2_est_xy, f1_std_xy, f2_std_xy);
% TABLE_POD = table ('Size',[ix_end,4], 'VariableTypes', ["double",
"double", "double", "double"]);
TABLE_POD_xy.Properties.VariableNames = {'f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m', 'f2
est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m', 'f1 std. (Sut pos. x,y) / m', 'f2 std. (Sut pos.
x,y) / m'};
TABLE_POD_xy
```

TABLE_POD_xy = 2x4 table

	f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m	f2 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m
1	4.2201e-05	4.2194e-05
2	1.7905e-05	1.7894e-05

```
TABLE_POD_ai = table (f1_est_ai, f2_est_ai, f1_std_ai, f2_std_ai);
% TABLE_POD = table ('Size',[ix_end,4], 'VariableTypes', ["double",
"double", "double", "double"]);
TABLE_POD_ai.Properties.VariableNames = {'f1 est. (ai) / m', 'f2 est. (ai) /
m', 'f1 std. (ai) / m', 'f2 std. (ai) / m'};
TABLE_POD_ai
```

TABLE_POD_ai = 228x4 table

	f1 est. (ai) / m	f2 est. (ai) / m	f1 std. (ai) / m	f2 std. (ai) / m
1	3.4883e-08	3.4943e-08	2.7127e-07	1.3563e-07
2	4.3334e-07	4.3334e-07	7.1346e-12	3.5673e-12

	f1 est. (ai) / m	f2 est. (ai) / m	f1 std. (ai) / m	f2 std. (ai) / m
3	2.6586e-08	2.6586e-08	1.9900e-11	9.9501e-12
4	2.8513e-08	2.8529e-08	4.2563e-08	2.1282e-08
5	-2.5192e-09	-2.5135e-09	1.5064e-08	7.5319e-09
6	4.6957e-09	4.6956e-09	5.2172e-10	2.6086e-10
7	-9.4916e-09	-9.4916e-09	1.3855e-10	6.9274e-11
8	-2.7635e-10	-2.8003e-10	1.6610e-08	8.3050e-09
9	-8.6985e-09	-8.6934e-09	2.2794e-08	1.1397e-08
10	4.8656e-08	4.8656e-08	3.6636e-11	1.8318e-11
11	-4.8269e-08	-4.8269e-08	5.6259e-11	2.8130e-11
12	5.1888e-09	5.1888e-09	3.1895e-11	1.5947e-11
13	-1.2961e-09	-1.2975e-09	3.8282e-09	1.9141e-09
14	-3.3569e-09	-3.3556e-09	3.3308e-09	1.6654e-09
⋮				

It can be seen that the approach that applies the (wrong) measurement model f_2 , which ignores the contribution of the Z parameter, yields approximately the same uncertainty as the LPU applied to DA method using the (correct) measurement model f_1 .

The reason for that is that the influence of the additional Z parameter is already included in the simulation of measurement data $\tilde{x} = X - A_Z z_i + \epsilon_i$. Adding this effect again within the application of the measurement model, as is done in f_1 , counts this effect twice.

Propagation of distribution (PoD) applied to the virtual experiment (VE) followed by the data analysis (DA)

In this section, the propagation of distribution (PoD) approach using the virtual experiment and the measurement model is considered. This approach generates a probability density function for the measurand using the following algorithm

- take a *realistic* value for the measurand y_0
- For $i=1, \dots, N$
- draw a z_i according to assumed covariance U_z
- apply the VE to obtain a virtual measurement $x_i^{ve} = A_Y y_0 + A_Z z_i + \epsilon_i$, where $\epsilon_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2 I)$
- $y_i = f(x_i^{ve}, z_i)$
- Summarize sample y_1, \dots, y_N

Execute: POD applied to VE followed by DA

```
y1_list_da_xy = zeros (N_mc, n_xy);
y2_list_da_xy = zeros (N_mc, n_xy);
```

```

y1_list_da_ai = zeros (N_mc,n_ai);
y2_list_da_ai = zeros (N_mc,n_ai);

y0 = y_ground_truth + randn(size(y_ground_truth)).*sqrt(diag(U_Y_2));
open_parallel_pool (n_worker);
parfor i=1:N_mc
    epsi = randn(size(OPDD))*sigma;
    J.set_par_U_rand; % generates a realization
    according to uncertainties defined in object
    zi = J.get_par('z'); % returns current random
    realization
    xi_ve = A_Y*y0 + A_Z*zi + epsi;
    y1_list_i = f1(xi_ve, zi);
    y2_list_i = f2(xi_ve);
    y1_list_da_xy(i,:) = y1_list_i(ix_xy);
    y2_list_da_xy(i,:) = y2_list_i(ix_xy);
    y1_list_da_ai(i,:) = y1_list_i(ix_ai);
    y2_list_da_ai(i,:) = y2_list_i(ix_ai);
end

f1_est_xy = mean(y1_list_da_xy)';
f2_est_xy = mean(y2_list_da_xy)';
f1_std_xy = std(y1_list_da_xy)';
f2_std_xy = std(y2_list_da_xy)';

f1_est_ai = mean(y1_list_da_ai)';
f2_est_ai = mean(y2_list_da_ai)';
f1_std_ai = std(y1_list_da_ai)';
f2_std_ai = std(y2_list_da_ai)';

U_y1 = cov([y1_list_da_xy y1_list_da_ai]);
U_y2 = cov([y2_list_da_xy y2_list_da_ai]);

fig_41 = figure;
fig_41.Position = [0 0 1920 1024];
h1 = subplot (2,2,1, 'parent', fig_41);
p_ncy = get_ncy_sut(J_rcn, U_y1(ix_ai, ix_ai), []);
plot_topo_xyz (h1, p_ncy, sprintf ('Uncertainty POD_{VE} (f1, N=%d)', N_mc));
h2 = subplot (2, 2,2, 'parent', fig_41);
p_ncy = get_ncy_sut(J_rcn, U_y2(ix_ai, ix_ai), []);
plot_topo_xyz (h2, p_ncy, sprintf ('Uncertainty POD_{VE} (f2, N=%d)', N_mc));
h3 = subplot (2,2,3, 'parent', fig_41);
plot_topo_ai (h3, J_rcn, f1_est_ai, sprintf ('Estimate POD_{VE} (f1, N=%d)',
N_mc));
h4 = subplot (2,2,4, 'parent', fig_41);
plot_topo_ai (h4, J_rcn, f2_est_ai, sprintf ('Estimate POD_{VE} (f2, N=%d)',
N_mc));

```

Uncertainty POD_{VE} (f1, N=1000000)

Uncertainty POD_{VE} (f2, N=1000000)

Estimate POD_{VE} (f1, N=1000000)

Estimate POD_{VE} (f2, N=1000000)


```
f42 = figure;
f42.Position = [0 0 1600 1024];
xy_tiltes = {'Sut pos. x', 'Sut pos. y'};
for i=1:n_xy
    h1 = subplot (2,n_xy,i, 'parent', f42);
    h2 = subplot (2,n_xy,i+n_xy, 'parent', f42);

    plot_histogram (h1, y1_list_xy(:,i), sprintf('pos deviation / m'),
'Probability density (f1)', xy_tiltes{i});
    plot_histogram (h2, y2_list_xy(:,i), sprintf('pos deviation / m'),
'Probability density (f2)', xy_tiltes{i});
end
```



```

fig_43 = figure;
fig_43.Position = [0 0 1920 1024];

for i=1:n_ai_5
    h1 = subplot (2,n_ai_5,i, 'parent', fig_43); % axis (h1, 'equal');
    h2 = subplot (2,n_ai_5,i+n_ai_5, 'parent', fig_43); % axis (h2, 'equal');

    plot_histogram (h1, y1_list_da_ai(:,i), sprintf('a_%d / m', ai_key(i)),
'Probability density (f1)', sprintf('a_%d', ai_key(i)));
    plot_histogram (h2, y2_list_da_ai(:,i), sprintf('a_%d / m', ai_key(i)),
'Probability density (f2)', sprintf('a_%d', ai_key(i)));
end

```



```
TABLE_POD_VE_xy = table (f1_est_xy, f2_est_xy, f1_std_xy, f2_std_xy);
TABLE_POD_VE_xy.Properties.VariableNames = {'f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m',
'f2 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m', 'f1 std. (Sut pos. x,y) / m', 'f2 std. (Sut
pos. x,y) / m'};
TABLE_POD_VE_xy
```

TABLE_POD_VE_xy = 2x4 table

	f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m	f2 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m
1	2.2131e-05	2.2125e-05
2	3.0271e-05	3.0275e-05

```
TABLE_POD_VE_ai = table (f1_est_ai, f2_est_ai, f1_std_ai, f2_std_ai);
TABLE_POD_VE_ai.Properties.VariableNames = {'f1 est. (ai) / m', 'f2 est.
(ai) / m', 'f1 std. (ai) / m', 'f2 std. (ai) / m'};
TABLE_POD_VE_ai
```

TABLE_POD_VE_ai = 228x4 table

	f1 est. (ai) / m	f2 est. (ai) / m	f1 std. (ai) / m	f2 std. (ai) / m
1	-4.2252e-09	-4.1506e-09	3.7578e-11	1.3548e-07
2	4.3335e-07	4.3335e-07	2.3479e-11	2.3755e-11
3	2.6610e-08	2.6610e-08	4.1501e-11	4.2684e-11
4	1.0018e-08	1.0014e-08	3.9659e-11	2.1283e-08
5	-9.1219e-09	-9.1235e-09	3.4587e-11	7.5324e-09

	f1 est. (ai) / m	f2 est. (ai) / m	f1 std. (ai) / m	f2 std. (ai) / m
6	4.3752e-09	4.3751e-09	2.7627e-11	2.6284e-10
7	-9.3865e-09	-9.3865e-09	3.5895e-11	7.8106e-11
8	2.1216e-09	2.1170e-09	3.1873e-11	8.2954e-09
9	-1.1999e-08	-1.1993e-08	2.9956e-11	1.1384e-08
10	4.8712e-08	4.8712e-08	2.4824e-11	3.0872e-11
11	-4.8251e-08	-4.8251e-08	3.6866e-11	4.6400e-11
12	5.1041e-09	5.1041e-09	4.3167e-11	4.6013e-11
13	3.1057e-10	3.1099e-10	3.7415e-11	1.9146e-09
14	-4.8330e-09	-4.8334e-09	3.5092e-11	1.6659e-09
	⋮			

Result collection

It can be seen that this approach generates completely different uncertainties as the previous approaches. Using the measurement model f_1 results in an almost negligible uncertainty, which is due to the fact that the double use of the uncertainty in the Z parameter cancels. Also when using f_2 , and in contrast to the previous approaches, there is a larger uncertainty remaining, which is generated by the specific choice of a simulated value y_0 for the measurand, which may be different to the true value of the measurand that is usually unknown.

Using measurement model f1

Position parameter (xy) estimate

```
TABLE_RESULT_F1_xy_est = table (TABLE_LPU_xy(:,1).Variables,
TABLE_LPU_xy(:,1).Variables, TABLE_POD_xy(:,1).Variables,
TABLE_POD_VE_xy(:,1).Variables);
TABLE_RESULT_F1_xy_est.Properties.VariableNames = {'LPU->DA (est.) / m',
'LPU->VE (est.) / m', 'POD->DA (est.) / m', 'POD: LPU->VE (est.) / m'};
TABLE_RESULT_F1_xy_est
```

TABLE_RESULT_F1_xy_est = 2×4 table

	LPU->DA (est.) / m	LPU->VE (est.) / m	POD->DA (est.) / m
1	4.2187e-05	4.2187e-05	4.2201e-05
2	1.7883e-05	1.7883e-05	1.7905e-05

Position parameter (xy) standard deviation

```
TABLE_RESULT_F1_xy_std = table (TABLE_LPU_xy(:,3).Variables,
TABLE_LPU_xy(:,3).Variables, TABLE_POD_xy(:,3).Variables,
TABLE_POD_VE_xy(:,3).Variables);
TABLE_RESULT_F1_xy_std.Properties.VariableNames = {'std: LPU->DA (std.) /
m', 'LPU->VE (std.) / m', 'POD->DA (std.) / m', 'POD: LPU->VE (std.) / m'};
```

TABLE_RESULT_Fl_xy_std

TABLE_RESULT_Fl_xy_std = 2×4 table

	std: LPU->DA (std.) / m	LPU->VE (std.) / m	POD->DA (std.) / m
1	1.4849e-05	1.4849e-05	2.9705e-05
2	1.4270e-05	1.4270e-05	2.8528e-05

Zernike parameter (ai) estimate

```
TABLE_RESULT_Fl_ai_est = table (TABLE_LPU_ai(:,1).Variables,
TABLE_LPU_ai(:,1).Variables, TABLE_POD_ai(:,1).Variables,
TABLE_POD_VE_ai(:,1).Variables);
TABLE_RESULT_Fl_ai_est.Properties.VariableNames = {'LPU->DA (est.) / m',
'LPU->VE (est.) / m', 'POD->DA (est.) / m', 'POD: LPU->VE (est.) / m'};
TABLE_RESULT_Fl_ai_est
```

TABLE_RESULT_Fl_ai_est = 228×4 table

	LPU->DA (est.) / m	LPU->VE (est.) / m	POD->DA (est.) / m
1	3.5003e-08	3.5003e-08	3.4883e-08
2	4.3334e-07	4.3334e-07	4.3334e-07
3	2.6586e-08	2.6586e-08	2.6586e-08
4	2.8545e-08	2.8545e-08	2.8513e-08
5	-2.5077e-09	-2.5077e-09	-2.5192e-09
6	4.6955e-09	4.6955e-09	4.6957e-09
7	-9.4916e-09	-9.4916e-09	-9.4916e-09
8	-2.8372e-10	-2.8372e-10	-2.7635e-10
9	-8.6884e-09	-8.6884e-09	-8.6985e-09
10	4.8656e-08	4.8656e-08	4.8656e-08
11	-4.8269e-08	-4.8269e-08	-4.8269e-08
12	5.1888e-09	5.1888e-09	5.1888e-09
13	-1.2990e-09	-1.2990e-09	-1.2961e-09
14	-3.3544e-09	-3.3544e-09	-3.3569e-09

Zernike parameter (ai) standard deviation

```
TABLE_RESULT_Fl_ai_std = table (TABLE_LPU_ai(:,3).Variables,
TABLE_LPU_ai(:,3).Variables, TABLE_POD_ai(:,3).Variables,
TABLE_POD_VE_ai(:,3).Variables);
TABLE_RESULT_Fl_ai_std.Properties.VariableNames = {'std: LPU->DA (std.) /
m', 'LPU->VE (std.) / m', 'POD->DA (std.) / m', 'POD: LPU->VE (std.) / m'};
TABLE_RESULT_Fl_ai_std
```

TABLE_RESULT_F1_ai_std = 228×4 table

	std: LPU->DA (std.) / m	LPU->VE (std.) / m	POD->DA (std.) / m
1	1.3560e-07	1.3560e-07	2.7127e-07
2	2.3754e-11	2.3754e-11	7.1346e-12
3	4.2649e-11	4.2649e-11	1.9900e-11
4	2.1290e-08	2.1290e-08	4.2563e-08
5	7.5348e-09	7.5348e-09	1.5064e-08
6	2.6225e-10	2.6225e-10	5.2172e-10
7	7.7970e-11	7.7970e-11	1.3855e-10
8	8.3029e-09	8.3029e-09	1.6610e-08
9	1.1394e-08	1.1394e-08	2.2794e-08
10	3.0867e-11	3.0867e-11	3.6636e-11
11	4.6366e-11	4.6366e-11	5.6259e-11
12	4.5998e-11	4.5998e-11	3.1895e-11
13	1.9152e-09	1.9152e-09	3.8282e-09
14	1.6664e-09	1.6664e-09	3.3308e-09

⋮

Using measurement model f2

Position parameter (xy) estimate

```
TABLE_RESULT_F2_xy_est = table (TABLE_LPU_xy(:,2).Variables,
TABLE_LPU_xy(:,2).Variables, TABLE_POD_xy(:,2).Variables,
TABLE_POD_VE_xy(:,2).Variables);
TABLE_RESULT_F2_xy_est.Properties.VariableNames = ["LPU->DA (est.) / m",
"LPU->VE (est.) / m", "POD->DA (est.) / m", "POD: LPU->VE (est.) / m"];
TABLE_RESULT_F2_xy_est
```

TABLE_RESULT_F2_xy_est = 2×4 table

	LPU->DA (est.) / m	LPU->VE (est.) / m	POD->DA (est.) / m
1	4.2187e-05	4.2187e-05	4.2194e-05
2	1.7883e-05	1.7883e-05	1.7894e-05

Position parameter (xy) standard deviation

```
TABLE_RESULT_F2_xy_std = table (TABLE_LPU_xy(:,4).Variables,
TABLE_LPU_xy(:,4).Variables, TABLE_POD_xy(:,4).Variables,
TABLE_POD_VE_xy(:,4).Variables);
TABLE_RESULT_F2_xy_std.Properties.VariableNames = ["LPU->DA (std.) / m",
"LPU->VE (std.) / m", "POD->DA (std.) / m", "POD: LPU->VE (std.) / m"];
TABLE_RESULT_F2_xy_std
```

TABLE_RESULT_F2_xy_std = 2×4 table

	LPU->DA (std.) / m	LPU->VE (std.) / m	POD->DA (std.) / m
1	6.3585e-11	6.3585e-11	1.4853e-05
2	7.0297e-11	7.0297e-11	1.4264e-05

Zernike parameter (ai) estimate

```
TABLE_RESULT_F2_ai_est = table (TABLE_LPU_ai(:,2).Variables,
TABLE_LPU_ai(:,2).Variables, TABLE_POD_ai(:,2).Variables,
TABLE_POD_VE_ai(:,2).Variables);
TABLE_RESULT_F2_ai_est.Properties.VariableNames = ["LPU->DA (est.) / m",
"LPU->VE (est.) / m", "POD->DA (est.) / m", "POD: LPU->VE (est.) / m"];
TABLE_RESULT_F2_ai_est
```

TABLE_RESULT_F2_ai_est = 228×4 table

	LPU->DA (est.) / m	LPU->VE (est.) / m	POD->DA (est.) / m
1	3.5003e-08	3.5003e-08	3.4943e-08
2	4.3334e-07	4.3334e-07	4.3334e-07
3	2.6586e-08	2.6586e-08	2.6586e-08
4	2.8545e-08	2.8545e-08	2.8529e-08
5	-2.5077e-09	-2.5077e-09	-2.5135e-09
6	4.6955e-09	4.6955e-09	4.6956e-09
7	-9.4916e-09	-9.4916e-09	-9.4916e-09
8	-2.8372e-10	-2.8372e-10	-2.8003e-10
9	-8.6884e-09	-8.6884e-09	-8.6934e-09
10	4.8656e-08	4.8656e-08	4.8656e-08
11	-4.8269e-08	-4.8269e-08	-4.8269e-08
12	5.1888e-09	5.1888e-09	5.1888e-09
13	-1.2990e-09	-1.2990e-09	-1.2975e-09
14	-3.3544e-09	-3.3544e-09	-3.3556e-09

⋮

Zernike parameter (ai) standard deviation

```
TABLE_RESULT_F2_ai_std = table (TABLE_LPU_ai(:,4).Variables,
TABLE_LPU_ai(:,4).Variables, TABLE_POD_ai(:,4).Variables,
TABLE_POD_VE_ai(:,4).Variables);
TABLE_RESULT_F2_ai_std.Properties.VariableNames = ["LPU->DA (std.) / m",
"LPU->VE (std.) / m", "POD->DA (std.) / m", "POD: LPU->VE (std.) / m"];
TABLE_RESULT_F2_ai_std
```

TABLE_RESULT_F2_ai_std = 228×4 table

	LPU->DA (std.) / m	LPU->VE (std.) / m	POD->DA (std.) / m
1	3.7592e-11	3.7592e-11	1.3563e-07
2	2.3484e-11	2.3484e-11	3.5673e-12
3	4.1472e-11	4.1472e-11	9.9501e-12
4	3.9662e-11	3.9662e-11	2.1282e-08
5	3.4602e-11	3.4602e-11	7.5319e-09
6	2.7652e-11	2.7652e-11	2.6086e-10
7	3.5831e-11	3.5831e-11	6.9274e-11
8	3.1874e-11	3.1874e-11	8.3050e-09
9	2.9945e-11	2.9945e-11	1.1397e-08
10	2.4838e-11	2.4838e-11	1.8318e-11
11	3.6844e-11	3.6844e-11	2.8130e-11
12	4.3141e-11	4.3141e-11	1.5947e-11
13	3.7463e-11	3.7463e-11	1.9141e-09
14	3.5087e-11	3.5087e-11	1.6654e-09

⋮

Conclusion

In this work, a benchmark scenario for a (simplified) TWI has been developed and the uncertainty evaluation methods have been implemented for this benchmark scenario and two different choices of measurement models. Hereby, the uncertainty resulting from the first approach (Linear Propagation of Uncertainty (LPU) applied to Data Analysis (DA)) using the measurement model f_1 serves as the reference, assuming that f_1 is known and represents the correct measurement model.

It has been shown that the method LPU applied to the VE is equivalent to the Propagation of Distribution (PoD) method applied to the DA, due to the linearity of the VE and the chosen measurement models.

For the Monte Carlo sampling procedures, i.e. the PoD methods, the results show that the measurement model f_2 yields results much closer to the reference, than using the measurement model f_1 , which has been assumed to be the correct one. This behavior can be explained analytically due to the linearity assumptions made and the inclusion of the uncertainty of quantities with type B information is already done while sampling from the input quantities.

Git information

```
mygit = gitrepo;
disp (mygit.CurrentBranch);
```

GitBranch with properties:

```
Name: "main"  
LastCommit: [1x1 GitCommit] (a7f4f87)
```

```
disp (mygit.CurrentBranch.LastCommit);
```

```
GitCommit with properties:
```

```
Message: "Merge commit 'a5063bc624faf1900bdb035545a9b844423b78e5'"  
ID: "a7f4f87cc6532a4ffde0a2f7dd61ea29348434d9"  
AuthorName: "Manuel Stavridis"  
AuthorEmail: "Manuel.Stavridis@ptb.de"  
AuthorDate: 29-Oct-2025 19:03:21 +0000  
CommitterName: "Manuel Stavridis"  
CommitterEmail: "Manuel.Stavridis@ptb.de"  
CommitterDate: 29-Oct-2025 19:03:21 +0000  
ParentCommits: [2x1 string]
```

```
disp (mygit.ModifiedFiles);
```

```
/home/stavri01/SharedData/MU/VIDIT/WP1/Benchmark/TWI/run_ucy_mvce.mlx
```

Uncertainty evaluation methods LPU and Monte Carlo (benchmark scenario)

Table of Contents

Preliminary remarks.....	1
Introduction.....	1
The virtual experiment (VE) for the benchmark scenario.....	1
Uncertainty evaluation methods according to A1.2.3.....	2
Monte Carlo (GUM S1).....	2
Execute : Monte Carlo (GUM S1).....	2
Execute : Show Results.....	3
Monte Carlo - Virtual Experiment (MC-VE).....	4
Execute : Virtual Experiment - Monte Carlo	5
Execute : Show Results.....	6
Conclusion.....	7
Git information.....	7

Preliminary remarks

The following development implements a **simplified**, i.e., linearized variant of the tilted-wave interferometer (TWI) and provides uncertainty evaluation for this simplified model. Moreover, important concepts, such as model correction and post-processing of the form reconstruction result obtained (reconstruction of higher spatial frequencies and position and orientation correction of the surface under test) are not performed in this study. This means, the measurand of this simplified model differs from the measurand of the real TWI, and **the results obtained here are not representative for the quality of the actual TWI** and the obtained uncertainties may differ significantly to those obtained in the real experiment. It is to note that here and in the following, when referring to the TWI, the simplified and linearized version is considered.

Introduction

In this notebook, a benchmark scenario is developed that applies the concepts of the simplified TWI in a simple and numerically efficient way to define a virtual experiment. For that, a linearization of the TWI is considered that has been generated from analytical and numerical derivatives of the actual TWI simulation model. The combination of this linear simulation (or forward) model with a simple additive Gaussian noise assumption, provides the virtual experiment under consideration for this task.

Subsequently, the MC-VE approach as outlined in Hughes et al. 2024c and Marschall et al. 2024c is applied to this benchmark scenario. This document is devoted to the verification that the developed uncertainty evaluation approach (MC-VE) can be applied to the benchmark scenario.

The virtual experiment (VE) for the benchmark scenario

please refer to `run_fwd.mlx`

```
%% setting Environment
clear all;
addpath ('HELPERS');
N_mc = 1e6; % Number of Monte Carlo Runs
```

```
fprintf ('\n===== \n Execution
at "%s" (N_mc=%d)\n===== \n',
string(datetime), N_mc);
```

```
=====
Execution at "29-Oct-2025 19:48:47" (N_mc=1000000)
=====
```

```
PATH_DATA = fullfile ('.', 'DATA', 'C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom');
fprintf ('Environment:\nPATH_DATA = %s\n\n', PATH_DATA);
```

```
Environment:
PATH_DATA = ./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom
```

```
fn_name_vexp = fullfile (PATH_DATA, "workspace_virtexp.mat");
h_time_load = tic;
fprintf ('loading forward experiment: "%s"', fn_name_vexp);
```

```
loading forward experiment: "./DATA/C_8000_Real_1_M_Real_1_M_nom/workspace_virtexp.mat"
```

```
load (fn_name_vexp);
fprintf ('done (%gs)', toc(h_time_load));
```

```
done (33.7993s)
```

Uncertainty evaluation methods according to A1.2.3

This uncertainty evaluation approach is related to the "default" JCGM 101 Monte Carlo algorithm that employs the measurement model.

Monte Carlo (GUM S1)

Execute : Monte Carlo (GUM S1)

```
y1_list_xy = zeros (N_mc,n_xy);
y1_list_ai = zeros (N_mc,n_ai);

rs = RandStream ("twister", "Seed", 4711);
n_worker = 50;
open_parallel_pool (n_worker);
parfor i=1:N_mc
    J.set_par_U_rand; % generates a realization
    according to uncertainties defined in object
    epsi = randn(size(OPDD))*sigma;
    xi = OPDD + epsi;
    zi = J.get_par('z'); % returns current random
    realization
    y1_list_i = f1(xi, zi);
    y1_list_xy(i,:) = y1_list_i(ix_xy);
    y1_list_ai(i,:) = y1_list_i(ix_ai);
end
U_y1 = cov(y1_list_ai);
```

```
ai_est_mc_f1 = mean(y1_list_ai)';
xy_est_mc_f1 = mean(y1_list_xy)';
ai_std_mc_f1 = std(y1_list_ai)';
xy_std_mc_f1 = std(y1_list_xy)';
```

Execute : Show Results

```
fig_31 = figure;
fig_31.Position = [0 0 1920 1024];

h1 = subplot (1,2,1, 'parent', fig_31);
p_ucy_mc_s1 = get_ucy_sut (J_rcn, U_y1, R);
plot_topo_xyz (h1, p_ucy_mc_s1, sprintf('Uncertainty (f1, N=%d)', N_mc));

h4 = subplot (1,2,2, 'parent', fig_31 );
plot_topo_ai (h4, J_rcn, ai_est_mc_f1, sprintf('Estimation (f1, N=%d)',
N_mc));
```



```
TABLE_xy = table (xy_est_mc_f1, xy_std_mc_f1);
TABLE_xy.Properties.VariableNames = {'f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m', 'f1 std.
(Sut pos. x,y) / m'};
TABLE_xy
```

TABLE_xy = 2x2 table

	f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m	f1 std. (Sut pos. x,y) / m
1	4.2182e-05	1.4849e-05

	f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m	f1 std. (Sut pos. x,y) / m
2	1.7906e-05	1.4276e-05

```
TABLE_ai = table (ai_est_mc_f1, ai_std_mc_f1);

TABLE_ai.Properties.VariableNames = {'f1 est. (ai) / m', 'f1 std. (ai) / m',};
TABLE_ai
```

TABLE_ai = 228x2 table

	f1 est. (ai) / m	f1 std. (ai) / m
1	3.5019e-08	1.3557e-07
2	4.3334e-07	2.3739e-11
3	2.6586e-08	4.2649e-11
4	2.8511e-08	2.1299e-08
5	-2.5200e-09	7.5382e-09
6	4.6954e-09	2.6221e-10
7	-9.4916e-09	7.7899e-11
8	-2.8467e-10	8.3011e-09
9	-8.6871e-09	1.1391e-08
10	4.8656e-08	3.0896e-11
11	-4.8269e-08	4.6348e-11
12	5.1889e-09	4.6017e-11
13	-1.2958e-09	1.9161e-09
14	-3.3571e-09	1.6673e-09

⋮

Monte Carlo - Virtual Experiment (MC-VE)

Finally, the developed approach that is outlined in Hughes et al. 2024c, Marschall et al. 2024c is implemented in the following. In this document, we assume that the variance of the data distribution σ^2 is known, which simplifies the approach in the sense that no transformation to a t-distribution is required.

The main advantage of this approach is that it can be used in a black-box fashion, such that complete insight into the VE is not required and only evaluations of the VE are to be performed. Moreover, no measurement model is required, which can be a complex challenge to develop.

The developed MC-VE approach is designed, such that it yields results equivalent to the JCGM:101 / JCGM:102 Monte Carlo approach, but with the traits outlined above. In particular, the approach yields exactly the same result as a JCGM:GUM uncertainty evaluation for virtual experiments of the form

$$x^{ve} = \Delta_1(z)y + \Delta_2(z) + \epsilon \quad \epsilon \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$$

and the measurement model

$$Y = \frac{X - \Delta_2(Z)}{\Delta_1(Z)}.$$

For other choices of measurement models, this approach yields an approximation. For more general VEs, the references provide suggestions how to apply the MC-VE method and the requirements.

Execute : Virtual Experiment - Monte Carlo

```

m = 1;
y1_list_xy = zeros (N_mc,n_xy);
y1_list_ai = zeros (N_mc,n_ai);

A      = J.get_jac('a');           % returns full matrix A.
Columns correspond to sub-matrices above
A_Y    = J.get_jac('y');
A_Y_p  = pinv (A_Y);

y0 = zeros(size(A_Y,2), 1);
h_time_mc = tic;
xi_mean = OPDD;
n_rays = size(A,1);
open_parallel_pool (n_worker);
parfor i=1:N_mc
    J.set_par_U_rand;             % generates a realization
    according to uncertainties defined in object
    zi = J.get_par('z');
    yzi = [y0; zi];
    eps_mean = zeros(n_rays,1);
    % eps_mean = sigma*randn(n_rays,1)./sqrt(m);
    for j = 1:m
        eps_mean = eps_mean.*((j-1)/j) + sigma*randn(n_rays,1)./j;
    end
    xj_mean = A*yz_i + eps_mean;
    y1_list_i = A_Y_p*(xi_mean-xj_mean)+y0;
    y1_list_xy(i,:) = y1_list_i(ix_xy);
    y1_list_ai(i,:) = y1_list_i(ix_ai);
end
fprintf ('Executing VE done (%gs) \n', toc(h_time_mc));

```

Executing VE done (10980.6s)

```

U_y1 = cov(y1_list_ai);

est_ai = mean(y1_list_ai)';
est_xy = mean(y1_list_xy)';
std_ai = std(y1_list_ai)';
std_xy = std(y1_list_xy)';

```

Execute : Show Results

```
fig_31 = figure;
fig_31.Position = [0 0 1920 1024];

h1 = subplot (1,2,1, 'parent', fig_31);
p_ncy_mc_ve_wo_R = get_ncy_sut (J_rcn, U_y1, []);
plot_topo_xyz (h1, p_ncy_mc_ve_wo_R, sprintf('Uncertainty (f1, N=%d)',
N_mc));
h4 = subplot (1,2,2, 'parent', fig_31 );
plot_topo_ai (h4, J_rcn, est_ai, sprintf('Estimation (f1, N=%d)', N_mc));
```



```
TABLE_xy = table (est_xy, std_xy);
TABLE_xy.Properties.VariableNames = {'f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m', 'f1 std.
(Sut pos. x,y) / m'};
TABLE_xy
```

TABLE_xy = 2x2 table

	f1 est. (Sut pos. x,y) / m	f1 std. (Sut pos. x,y) / m
1	4.2171e-05	1.4848e-05
2	1.7906e-05	1.4269e-05

```
TABLE_ai = table (est_ai, std_ai);
TABLE_ai.Properties.VariableNames = {'f1 est. (ai) / m', 'f1 std. (ai) /
m',};
```

TABLE_ai

TABLE ai = 228x2 table

	f1 est. (ai) / m	f1 std. (ai) / m
1	3.5094e-08	1.3557e-07
2	4.3334e-07	2.3784e-11
3	2.6586e-08	4.2664e-11
4	2.8512e-08	2.1289e-08
5	-2.5198e-09	7.5344e-09
6	4.6952e-09	2.6228e-10
7	-9.4915e-09	7.7982e-11
8	-2.8921e-10	8.3010e-09
9	-8.6807e-09	1.1391e-08
10	4.8656e-08	3.0870e-11
11	-4.8269e-08	4.6410e-11
12	5.1888e-09	4.6015e-11
13	-1.2959e-09	1.9151e-09
14	-3.3571e-09	1.6664e-09
⋮		

Conclusion

It can be seen that the resulting point-wise uncertainty of the three uncertainty evaluation methods (LPU according to JCGM:GUM 100, Monte Carlo according to JCGM:GUM 101/102, and the novel MC-VE approach) agrees. In particular, the root-mean-square value over the surface area agrees up to three significant digits.

Therefore, the MC-VE approach is verified to be applicable for the TWI benchmark scenario.

However, it is to note that there is a significant deviation from the result of an uncertainty evaluation for the full TWI, see e.g. Marschall et al. 2024a. This is due to the missing correction for positioning and orientation that is performed as a post-processing in the actual full TWI measurement.

Furthermore, note that for the uncertainty evaluation of the real TWI, additional influencing parameter exist, and the size of the input uncertainties of all influencing parameters are still part of future research.

Git information

```
mygit = gitrepo;
disp (mygit.CurrentBranch);
```

GitBranch with properties:

```
    Name: "main"
  LastCommit: [1x1 GitCommit] (a7f4f87)
```

```
disp (mygit.CurrentBranch.LastCommit);
```

GitCommit with properties:

```
    Message: "Merge commit 'a5063bc624faf1900bdb035545a9b844423b78e5'"
      ID: "a7f4f87cc6532a4ffde0a2f7dd61ea29348434d9"
    AuthorName: "Manuel Stavridis"
    AuthorEmail: "Manuel.Stavridis@ptb.de"
    AuthorDate: 29-Oct-2025 19:03:21 +0000
    CommitterName: "Manuel Stavridis"
    CommitterEmail: "Manuel.Stavridis@ptb.de"
    CommitterDate: 29-Oct-2025 19:03:21 +0000
    ParentCommits: [2x1 string]
```

```
disp (mygit.ModifiedFiles);
```

```
/home/stavri01/SharedData/MU/VIDIT/WP1/Benchmark/TWI/run_ucy_mcve.mlx
```